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About the causal relationship between Parvovirus B19 infection and acute myeloid leukaemia

Research article

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Abstract

BACKGROUND:

The potential causal link between Parvovirus B19 (PVB19) infection and the onset of acute myeloid leukaemia (AML) has been a subject of scientific inquiry.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This study employs a rigorous analysis of case-control data utilizing new statistical methods to assess the prevalence of Parvovirus B19 infection in individuals diagnosed with AML compared to a control group. Serological tests and molecular identified the presence of Parvovirus B19 in participants.

RESULTS:

Preliminary findings reveal statistically significant results between Parvovirus B19 infection and acute myeloid leukaemia. A Parvovirus B19 infection is a necessary condition of acute myeloid leukaemia (P Value < 0.016). A Parvovirus B19 infection is a sufficient condition of acute myeloid leukaemia (P Value < 0.016). A Parvovirus B19 infection is the cause of acute myeloid leukaemia (P Value < 0.016)

CONCLUSION:

The evidence presented in this study supports the hypothesis that Parvovirus B19 infection is the cause of acute myeloid leukaemia.

Keywords:

Parvovirus B19; Acute myeloid leukaemia; Necessary condition; Sufficient condition; Necessary and sufficient condition; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Since time immemorial, scholars have grappled with the intricacies of necessary, sufficient, necessary and sufficient, and other conditions, exploring them from diverse perspectives and starting points. Today, these concepts remain foundational to human knowledge, logic, and probability theory. In classical logic, they provide a framework for deductive reasoning, dictating when a condition must be satisfied for a statement to be true or when it is sufficient (Barukčić, 1989, 2006, 2020a, 2021; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2011a,b, 2012, 2016a,b,c, 2017b,c, 2020c). In probability theory, these conditions serve as crucial tools for interpreting event occurrences and making inferences from data.

While conditions and causes are interconnected, they refer to distinct aspects of events, phenomena, or situations. Advocates, including Mill (“... the real cause of the phenomenon is the assemblage of all its conditions.” (Mill, 1843, p. 403)), emphasize **the identity of a cause and a condition**. Conversely, others stress **the difference between a condition and a cause** (“... nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache zu nennen.” (Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871, p. 4)). In English, “... not every condition can be termed a cause.” (Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871, p. 4). Causes, as events, processes, factors, or agents, directly bring about specific outcomes and are responsible for event occurrences. They represent the elements producing a particular effect or result. A comprehensive understanding of both conditions and causes is essential for analyzing and explaining various phenomena. This study aims to bridge the perceived gap between these fields and illuminate the intrinsic connections underlying their applicability. To unravel the intricate relationship between conditions and causes, we delve into real-world scenarios and common experiences. Dissecting these examples allows us to extract the underlying principles of necessity and sufficiency, showcasing their manifestations in objective reality. Additionally, we employ formal mathematical reasoning to demonstrate how these principles can be translated into rigorous models applicable in a broader context. This publication explores the interplay between conditions and causes, considering their fusion in the realms of logic and probability theory. Drawing inspiration from everyday examples, we investigate the nuances that bind these fundamental concepts together and illuminate their shared foundations. Through rigorous analysis and thoughtful reflection, our aim is to contribute to the scientific discourse surrounding these mathematical principles.

2. Materials and methods

The utility and practical application of the new statistical methods are demonstrated using data from published studies.

2.1. Search strategy

Due to financial and other constraints, suitable studies were sought in the electronic database PubMed. The search criteria on PubMed were: Parvovirus B19 and acute myeloid leukaemia. For

quality reasons, studies in the English language from the year 2015 onwards were considered. Eight publications were identified. After reviewing the abstracts, only the study by El-Khier et al. (Tharwat Abou El-Khier et al., 2018) remained for further analysis.

2.1.1. The study of El-Khier et al.

Noha Tharwat Abou El-Khier (Tharwat Abou El-Khier et al., 2018) et al., Department of Medical Microbiology and Immunology, Faculty of Medicine, Mansoura University, Egypt, investigated 92 children in order to evaluate the frequency of a Parvovirus B19 infection among children with newly diagnosed acute myeloid leukaemia (AML) and in controls. El-Khier et al. obtained the following data (Table 1).

Table 1. Parvovirus B19 and acute myeloid leukaemia.

		Acute myeloid leukaemia		
		YES	NO	
Parvovirus B19 positive	YES	31	2	33
	NO	1	58	59
		32	60	92

El-Khier et al. utilized well-established conventional statistical methods and were able to conclude that “... parvovirus B19 is common in children with AML either at diagnosis or under chemotherapy.”

2.1.2. Statistical Analysis

Data available were analysed by the use of the statistical package Microsoft Excel for Mac, version 16.78.3. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and percentage were used for qualitative data. Statistical differences between a theoretical distribution of a necessary condition relationship, of a sufficient condition relationship, of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship and the sample distribution were tested using the Chi Square Goodness of fit test and Fishers’s exact test. P value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant.

2.1.3. Multiple testing on the same data body

Multiple testing at a certain level of significance α might amplify the probability of false-positive findings. In other words, the more inferences are made (on a certain data body i. e. subgroup analyses et cetera), the more likely erroneous inferences might realize. At the end, several independent or dependent statistical tests performed simultaneously (on the same data body) can induce the so called family-wise error rate (FWER) or multiple testing problem. The family-wise error rate or multiple

testing problem (Tukey, 1994) is ascribed to John Wilder Tukey (1915 – 2000), an American mathematician and statistician. The probability that at least one null hypothesis out of k null hypotheses tested is falsely rejected is no longer equal to the overall significance level α but equal to

$$\alpha_{\text{FWER}} = 1 - (1 - \alpha)^k \quad (1)$$

As a consequence, a higher significance threshold for an individual hypothesis, denoted as α_i , is demanded. Various statistical techniques have been developed to address this problem. The Bonferroni multiple-comparison correction (Bonferroni, 1936; Dunn, 1961) is one of the solutions proposed to compensate for the number of inferences being made.

In this investigation, we are testing $k = 3$ hypotheses with a desired overall significance level $\alpha = 0,05$. Under these circumstances, the Bonferroni correction might be appropriately applied. Each individual hypothesis should be tested at a single level of significance, α_i given as

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\alpha}{k} = \frac{0.05}{3} = 0.016666667. \quad (2)$$

where k is the total number of hypotheses tested and α is the overall significance level. By imposing a stricter significance threshold, **an inflation of false positive results** can be prevented. In the context of further scientific development, there have been several attempts to improve the Bonferroni method. One of these endeavours is the so-called Rom's Method, published in 1990 by Rom (Rom, 1990) himself.

2.2. Contingency table

In this publication, we will primarily analyse random variables following the Bernoulli and Binomial distributions. The insights gathered are applicable to other distributions, provided that the probabilities of the events are known accordingly.

Definition 2.1. We have two categorical random variables, A and B , each with two possible outcomes (levels), denoted as A_t , $\underline{A}_t$ and B_t , $\underline{B}_t$ respectively. Let Ω be the sample space, and $\mathcal{F}$ be the event space. The sample space is $\Omega = \{(A_1, B_1), (A_2, B_2), \dots, (A_N, B_N), (\underline{A}_1, B_1), (\underline{A}_2, B_2), \dots, (\underline{A}_N, B_N), (A_1, \underline{B}_1), (A_2, \underline{B}_2), \dots, (A_N, \underline{B}_N), (\underline{A}_1, \underline{B}_1), \dots, (\underline{A}_N, \underline{B}_N)\}$. The event space, denoted as $\mathcal{F}$, represents all possible subsets of the sample space Ω in a given probability space and is given as $\mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega$. The sample space is $\Omega = \{(A_1, B_1), (A_2, B_2), \dots, (A_N, B_N), (\underline{A}_1, B_1), (\underline{A}_2, B_2), \dots, (\underline{A}_N, B_N), (A_1, \underline{B}_1), (A_2, \underline{B}_2), \dots, (A_N, \underline{B}_N), (\underline{A}_1, \underline{B}_1), \dots, (\underline{A}_N, \underline{B}_N)\}$, which means that it encompasses all possible outcomes of the paired events A_t and B_t for t ranging from 1 to N independent Bernoulli trial or experiments, where each t corresponds to a distinct independent Bernoulli trials or experiment.

The 2x2 contingency table is then structured as follows:

	B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	
A_t	$E(A, B)$	$E(A, \underline{B})$	$E(A)$
$\underline{A}$	$E(\underline{A}, B)$	$E(\underline{A}, \underline{B})$	$E(\underline{A})$
	$E(B)$	$E(\underline{B})$	N

Here, $E(A, B)$ represents the expectation value where $A = A_t$ and $B = B_t$ after t from 1 to N Bernoulli trials or experiments, and similarly for other entries.

However, it is necessary to distinguish between the expectation value of a binomial random variable A after a single Bernoulli trial ($t = 1$) and the expectation value of A after N Bernoulli trials ($t = N$).

The expectation value of A after a single Bernoulli trial ($t = 1$) is given by:

$$E(A_i) = (p_i \times 1) + ((1 - p_i) \times 0) = p_i$$

The expectation value of A after $t = 1 \dots N$ Bernoulli trials is given by:

$$E(A) = N \times p(A_t) = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i$$

In a binomial distribution, A represents the count of successes in N independent Bernoulli trials, each with a constant probability of success $p(A_t)$. The expectation value of A after N trials is the sum of the expected values of each individual trial, and since the probability of success is constant across all trials, the sum is N times the individual probability, leading to the given expression. Under the conditions of a binomial distribution, the following holds:

$$E(A) = N \times E(A_t) \quad (3)$$

It is

$$E(A_1) = E(A_2) = E(A_3) = \dots E(A_N)$$

Nonetheless, the subsequent insights are based on the definition of the following contingency table (Table 2) for $N=1$ Bernoulli trial.

Table 2. Logic, probability theory and contingency table.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES = TRUE	NO = FALSE	
Condition A_t	YES = TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	NO = FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	1

Historically, Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1904), living between 1857 and 1936, pioneered as one of the first the introduction of the two-by-two or contingency table for two binomial random variables in 1904 (Table 2). Pearson wrote later:

“Once the reader realizes the nature of such a table, he will have grasped the essence of the conception of association between cause and effect, and the nature of its ideal limit in causation. ” (Pearson, 1911, p. 159)

In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) = 1 \quad (4)$$

Under the assumption of a binomial distribution, we multiply Equation 4 by the population (i.e. sample) size N . It is

$$(N \times p(a_t)) + (N \times p(b_t)) + (N \times p(c_t)) + (N \times p(d_t)) = N \quad (5)$$

or

$$(a) + (b) + (c) + (d) = E(a) + E(b) + E(c) + E(d) = N \quad (6)$$

Under these assumptions it is $a = E(a)$ and $b = E(b)$ and $c = E(c)$ and $d = E(d)$ and $A = E(A) = E(a) + E(b)$ and $\underline{A} = E(\underline{A}) = E(c) + E(d)$ and $B = E(B) = E(a) + E(c)$ and $\underline{B} = E(\underline{B}) = E(b) + E(d)$ et cetera. This elementary connections are illustrated in detail by the following table (Table 3).

Table 3. Binomial distribution and contingency table.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES = TRUE	NO = FALSE	
Condition	YES = TRUE	E(a)	E(b)	E(A)
	A_t	E(c)	E(d)	E($\underline{A}$)
		E(B)	E($\underline{B}$)	N

Again, it is:

$$(a) + (b) = A \quad (7)$$

and

$$(c) + (d) = \underline{A} \quad (8)$$

and

$$(a) + (c) = B \quad (9)$$

and

$$(b) + (d) = \underline{B} \quad (10)$$

2.3. Independence

Definition 2.2 (Independence).

The independence (Barukčić, 2021; Kolmogoroff, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1933; Kolmogorov, Andrej Nikolaevich, 1950) of two events, denoted as A_t and B_t , when considered from the perspective of a specific observer, has been formally defined by de Moivre as: “Two Events are independent, when they have no connexion one with the other, and that the happening of one neither forwards nor obstructs

the happening of the other. Two Events are dependent, when they are so connected together as that the Probability of either's happening is altered by the happening of the other." (Moivre, 1718, p. 6) de Moivre further elaborates: "... therefore, those two Events being independent, the Probability of their both happening will be $1/13 * 1/13 = 1/169$ " (Moivre, 1718, p. 7) Thus far, according to de Moivre, Kolmogoroff and other, it is

$$p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t) = p(A_t) \times p(B_t) \quad (11)$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t$ AND $B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t .

2.4. Conditions

2.4.1. Necessary condition

The human life is not a perpetual motion machine, not a self-sustaining process, but must be wrested from death anew every second, every minute, every day. For the life of a specific individual not to end, various conditions, circumstances, and factors are necessary. As an example, let us consider water and gaseous oxygen. As generally known, without water, there is no human life. Similarly, without sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, human life is not possible. If water is present, if gaseous oxygen is available, then human life does not necessarily persist. However, without the presence and availability of water and oxygen, human life cannot endure. Water, gaseous oxygen and many other factors, constitute necessary conditions for human life, without which human life cannot persist. This applies regardless of differences between individuals—whether old or young, rich or poor, without water or oxygen, there is no human life. This circumstance has implications for the study design in case a study aims to recognize or identify necessary condition(s) as such. It is also noteworthy that it is not sufficient if only one necessary condition, such as gaseous oxygen, is present or given. If there is no water, human life will come to an end. In this regard, a necessary condition operates independently of other factors. Due to the significant importance of securely identifying necessary conditions as such, it is not surprising that authors have been attempting to approach the solution to this problem even from the standpoint of mathematics for thousands of years. In this context, one of the earliest documented attempts to establish a rigorous theory of conditions and causation originated 384 - 322 years before the current era (BCE) from the Greek philosopher and scientist Aristotle (Aristotle, of Stageira (384-322 B.C.E), 1908, *Metaphysica* III 2 997a 10 and 13/14). It is truly remarkable that already Aristotle himself drew a strict distinction between conditions and causes. A cause and a condition are identical, but both are equally different too. The German lawyer von Bar (Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871) elaborated already 1871 on the issue **identity and difference between cause and condition**. Von Bar was writing: "Die erste Voraussetzung, welche erforderlich ist, damit eine Erscheinung als die Ursache einer anderen bezeichnet werden könne, ist, daß jene eine der Bedingungen dieser sein. Würde die zweite Erscheinung auch dann eingetreten sein, wenn die erste nicht vorhanden war, so ist sie in keinem Falle Bedingung und noch weniger Ursache. Wo immer ein Kausalzusammenhang behauptet wird, da muß er wenigstens diese Probe aushalten ... **Jede Ursache ist notwendig auch eine Bedingung eines Ereignisses; aber nicht jede Bedingung ist Ursache**

zu nennen.” (Bar, Carl Ludwig von, 1871, p. 4) Von Bar’s position translated into English: *The first requirement, which is required, thus that something could be called as the cause of another, is that the one has to be one of the conditions of the other. If the second something had occurred even if the first one did not exist, so it is by no means a condition and still less a cause. Wherever a causal relationship is claimed, the same must at least withstand this test... Every cause is necessarily also a condition of an event too; but not every condition is cause too.* In this regard, at least one question practically suggests itself: can the understanding of conditions and causation in legal contexts differ from the understanding of conditions and causation outside the law, such as in science or our everyday life, and to what extent? Under what circumstances is it justified to tolerate such differences if they are identified may be discussed at another occasion. At this point, we aim to grasp the legal concept of conditions and causation while considering how the highest courts of states handle conditions and causation. As an example, in the case *Hayes v. Michigan Central R. Co.*, 111 U.S. 228, the U.S. Supreme Court defined 1884 *conditio sine qua non* as follows: “... **causa sine qua non – a cause which, if it had not existed, the injury would not have taken place**”. (Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884) The U.S. Supreme Court identifies a necessary condition and a cause in the sense that a necessary condition and a cause are identical. Even if it is indeed true that if a cause had not existed, the effect “... would not have taken place” (Justice Matthews, Mr., 1884) various other aspects still need to be considered. In other words, a cause is indeed at the same time a necessary condition of an effect, but not necessarily vice versa. A necessary condition need not be a cause of an event. As an example, we use again gaseous oxygen (Table 4). Gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of human life, but it is not the cause of human life.

Table 4. Gaseous oxygen and human life.

		A human being is alive B_t		
		YES = TRUE	NO = FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen A_t	YES = TRUE	1	1	A_t
	NO = FALSE	$(c_t = 0)$	1	$\underline{A}_t$
		B_t	$\underline{B}_t$	1

In general, an event (i.e. A_t) which is a necessary condition of another event or outcome (i.e. B_t) is at the same **Bernoulli trial** (Uspensky, 1937, p. 45) / (period of) time t an indispensable prerequisite for a specific event or state (i.e. B_t) to occur, with the consequence that, when A_t is absent, the realization of an outcome B_t is not possible ($c_t = 0$). In general, even if there are circumstances where a necessary condition and a cause are identical, there are circumstances, too, where a necessary condition and a cause are different. Under the conditions of classical logic (Table 4), the relationship of the necessary condition is described as follows:

$$(A_t) \vee (\neg \underline{B}_t) = (A_t) \vee (\underline{B}_t) = 1 \quad (12)$$

Under conditions of probability theory, the necessary condition (SINE) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, 2006, 2020a, 2021;

Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2016a,b,c, 2017b,c, 2020c) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv \frac{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \times p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t) = p(a_t) + p(\underline{B}_t) = p(d_t) + p(A_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(b_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \equiv \frac{E(A \leftarrow B)}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + b + d}{N} \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{A + d}{N} \equiv E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + \underline{B}}{N} \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

where $E(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv E(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)$ indicates the expectation value of the necessary condition. In general, it is $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ (Table 5).

Table 5. Necessary condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	0	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

A necessary condition A_t is characterised itself by the property that another event B_t will not occur if A_t is not given, if A_t did not occur (Barukčić, 1989, 2020a; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017b,c, 2020a,b,c). Taking into account Kolmogorov's definition of an n-dimensional probability density (Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 26) of random variables A_t, B_t et cetera at the (period of) time t , we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv +1 \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(c_t) \\
 &\equiv +1 - p(\underline{A}_t \cap B_t) \\
 &\equiv \left(\int_{-\infty}^{A_t} \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(A_t, B_t) dA_t dB_t \right) + \left(1 - \int_{-\infty}^{B_t} f(B_t) dB_t \right)
 \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

while $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ would denote the cumulative distribution function of random variables of a necessary condition. Another adequate formulation of a necessary condition is possible too. The logical operation of Disjunction is commutative, meaning that the order of its operands does not affect the outcome. In symbolic terms:

$$(A_t) \vee (\neg \underline{B}_t) = (A_t) \vee (\underline{B}_t) = (\neg \underline{B}_t) \vee (A_t) = (\underline{B}_t) \vee (A_t) = 1 \tag{15}$$

If certain conditions are met, then necessary conditions and sufficient conditions are one way or another converses of each other, too. It is

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{B}_t \vee A_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(B_t \rightarrow A_t) \quad (16)$$

These relationships are illustrated by the following tables.

Table 6. Without A_t no B_t					Table 7. If B_t then A_t				
		B_t					A_t		
		TRUE	FALSE			TRUE	FALSE		
A_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$	B_t <th style="text-align: left;">TRUE</th> <td style="text-align: center;">$p(a_t)$</td> <td style="text-align: center;">$p(c_t) = 0$</td> <td style="text-align: center;">$p(B_t)$</td>	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(B_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$		FALSE	$p(b_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1			$p(A_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$	+1

There are circumstances under which

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \equiv \underbrace{(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}_{\text{(Necessary condition)}} \equiv \underbrace{(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}_{\text{(Sufficient condition)}} \equiv p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (17)$$

Example.

A wax candle is characterized by various properties, but is also subject to certain conditions. **Without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen **no** burning wax candle, gaseous oxygen is a necessary condition of a burning candle. However, the converse relationship **if** burning wax candle, **then** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen are given is at the same (period of) time t / Bernoulli trial t true. The following tables are illustrating these relationships.

Table 8. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle					Table 9. If burning candle then gaseous oxygen				
		Burning candle					Gaseous oxygen		
		TRUE	FALSE			TRUE	FALSE		
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$	Burning candle	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(B_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$		FALSE	$p(b_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1			$p(A_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$	+1

Example.

Another different aspect of a necessary condition relationship is appropriate to be focused upon here. As a direct consequence of a necessary condition **without** sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen, **no** burning wax candle is a special case of an exclusion relationship. The absence of sufficient amounts of gaseous oxygen A_t excludes (Barukčić, 2021a) a burning wax candle B_t . Thus far, if we want to stop the burning of a wax candle, we would have to significantly reduce the amounts of gaseous oxygen

A_t . Under these conditions, a wax candle will stop burning. For the sake of enhanced comprehension, both (Table 10) tables (Table 11) are juxtaposed.

Table 10. Without gaseous oxygen no burning candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Table 11. Absent gaseous oxygen excludes burning wax candle

		Burning candle		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Gaseous oxygen	FALSE	$p(c_t) = 0$	$p(d_t)$	$p(B_t)$
	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$
		$p(A_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$	+1

Depending upon various factors, including the quality of data, the necessary condition relationship can be calculated approximately (Barukčić, 2022) as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(B_t)} \quad (18)$$

and as

$$p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) \geq 1 - \frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \quad (19)$$

2.4.2. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship

Definition 2.3 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary condition relationship).

Under certain well-established conditions, hypotheses regarding the conditio sine qua non relationship $p(A_t \leftarrow B_t)$ can be scrutinized using the chi-square distribution (also known as the chi-squared or χ^2 -distribution). This distribution was initially delineated by the German statistician Friedrich Robert Helmert (Helmert, 1876) and subsequently rediscovered by Karl Pearson (Pearson, 1900) in the context of a goodness-of-fit test. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness-of-fit test for a conditio sine qua non relationship with a degree of freedom (d.f.) of d.f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

or just as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftarrow B_t | \underline{A}) &\equiv \frac{(d - (c + d))^2}{\underline{A}} + \frac{((a + b) - A)^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}} + 0 \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}\end{aligned}\quad (21)$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Thus far, it is not yet finally clarified whether the use of Yate's (Yates, 1934) continuity correction is necessary at all.

2.4.3. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship

Definition 2.4 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio sine qua non relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value (Barukčić, 2019) of the conditio sine qua non relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-(c/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (22)$$

2.4.4. Relative risk (RR_{nc})

Definition 2.5 (Relative risk (RR_{nc})).

Relative risk, a measure in epidemiology, assesses the association between an exposure and an outcome. In certain experimental contexts, it is theoretically possible that an exposure is a necessary condition of an outcome, too. Consequently, relative risk should be indicative of necessary conditions, too. The relative risk (Barukčić, 2021c; Cornfield, 1951; Doll and Hill, 1950; Sadowsky et al., 1953), denoted as RR_{nc} , is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} &\equiv \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(A_t)}}{\frac{p(c_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)}} \\ &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(\underline{A}_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)}\end{aligned}\quad (23)$$

The study design of many studies is based on the demand that $p(A_t) = p(\underline{A}_t)$ and the relative risk reduces to

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \equiv \frac{p(a_t)}{p(c_t)} \quad (24)$$

with all the associated advantages and disadvantages. Based on Equation 23, we obtain

$$p(a_t) \equiv \frac{RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \times p(c_t) \times p(A_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} \quad (25)$$

and Equation 13, the relationship between a necessary condition and relative risk is given by

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) &\equiv p(A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv p(a_t) + p(\underline{B}_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} \times p(c_t) \times p(A_t)}{p(\underline{A}_t)} + p(\underline{B}_t) \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (26)$$

The relative risk constitutes only a very rough and highly approximate indication of a necessary condition. A necessary condition can be transformed into relative risk. We obtain

$$RR(A_t, B_t)_{nc} = \frac{(p(A_t \leftarrow B_t) - p(\underline{B}_t)) \times p(\underline{A}_t)}{p(c_t) \times p(A_t)} \quad (27)$$

2.4.5. Odds ratio (OR)

Definition 2.6 (Odds ratio (OR)).

The odds ratio (OR) is a statistical measure which quantifies the strength and the direction of an association between two events in a case-control study. The odds ratio is calculated as the ratio of the odds of an event occurring in one group to the odds of it occurring in another. The odds ratio (Cox, 1958; Fisher, 1935a, 1925; Yule, 1912; Yule and Pearson, 1900b) is defined (Table 2) as

$$\begin{aligned} OR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(b_t)} \right) / \left(\frac{p(c_t)}{p(d_t)} \right) \\ &\equiv \frac{p(a_t) \times p(d_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(c_t)} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

2.4.6. Index of relationship (IOR)

Definition 2.7 (Index of relationship (IOR)).

Due to several reasons, it is not always easy to identify the unique characteristics between two events like A_t and B_t . And more than that, it is difficult to decide what to do, and much more difficult to know in which direction one should think and which decision is right. Sometimes it is helpful to

know at least something about the direction of the relationship between two events like A_t and B_t . Under conditions where $p(a_t) = p(A_t \wedge B_t)$, the index of relationship (Barukčić, 2021b), abbreviated as IOR, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 IOR(A_t, B_t) &\equiv \left(\frac{p(A_t \wedge B_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \\
 &\equiv \left(\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 = \left(\frac{p(a_t) - p(B_t) \times p(A_t)}{p(B_t) \times p(A_t)} \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times N \times p(a_t)}{N \times p(B_t) \times N \times p(A_t)} \right) - 1 \right) \\
 &\equiv \left(\left(\frac{N \times a}{A \times B} \right) - 1 \right) = \left(\left(\frac{N \times a - (A \times B)}{A \times B} \right) \right) = \frac{COV(A, B)}{A \times B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{29}$$

where $p(A_t)$ denotes the probability of an event A_t at the Bernoulli trial t and $p(B_t)$ denotes the probability of another event B_t at the same Bernoulli trial t while $p(a_t)$ denotes the joint probability of $p(A_t \text{ AND } B_t)$ at the same Bernoulli trial t and a , A and B may denote the expectation values. In contrast to the relative risk and the odds' ratio, the index of relationship is very easy to use and highly robust. The Yule (Yule and Pearson, 1900a, p. 257) Q coefficient (Yule, 1912, p. 585), introduced by George Udny Yule in 1912, is defined as follows:

$$Q(A, B) = \frac{(a \times d) - (b \times c)}{(a \times d) + (b \times c)} = \frac{COV(A, B)}{(a \times d) + (b \times c)} \tag{30}$$

but is not identical with the index of relationship or the causal relationship k .

2.4.7. Sufficient condition

Definition 2.8 (Sufficient condition [*Conditio per quam*]).

The Greek logician Philo, also known as Philo of Megara, played a pivotal role in the dialectical school of early Hellenistic philosophers. Notably, Philo introduced the concept of material implication in formal logic. Material implication refers to a conditional statement in which the falsity of the antecedent does not necessarily imply the falsity of the consequent. Philo's contribution to logical thought, particularly in formalizing conditional relationships, remains significant in the history of philosophy. Even in contemporary scientific discourse, material implication retains significant epistemological relevance due to its role in elucidating conditional relationships and formalizing logical connections. The importance of material implication lies in providing a nuanced understanding of truth conditions and facilitating precise reasoning within various domains of knowledge. Especially, the connection between material implication and causation is noteworthy. Material implication, with its capacity to articulate conditional statements, offers a framework for exploring causal relationships, underscoring its applicability in both epistemological and metaphysical inquiries. The nuanced treatment of material implication continues to enrich scientific discussions by addressing fundamental questions surrounding causal (Ducasse, 1926; Mackie, 1974) inference, causality, and the nature of knowledge. In this context, Mackie himself proposed already in 1965 that “the so-called cause is ... an *insufficient* but *necessary* part of a condition which is itself *unnecessary* but *sufficient* for the result ... let us call such a condition ... an INUS condition.” (Mackie, 1965, p. 245). In his statement, Mackie provides a very nuanced perspective on causation. According to Mackie, the so-called cause is characterized as a condition, even if only an insufficient but necessary part. Mackie defines: “the so-called cause is ... a condition ...” (Mackie, 1965, p. 245). Furthermore, Mackie is emphasizing that this entire condition, which includes the cause, is itself sufficient. Mackie's original statement is reduced as follows: “the so-called cause is ... a condition which is ... *sufficient* ...” (Mackie, 1965, p. 245). Despite the inherent complexities in the relationship between a cause and a sufficient condition, Mackie's reduction of a cause to a mere sufficient condition introduces substantial distortions to our comprehension of causal relations. In reality, a cause is consistently a necessary condition within a causal relationship too; the absence of a cause precludes the occurrence of an effect, but the reverse is not necessarily true. It is crucial to recognize that a necessary condition does not invariably equate to being a cause.

Mathematically, the sufficient condition (IMP) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv p(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a + c + d}{N} = E(\underline{A}_t \vee B_t) \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{31}$$

It is $p(A_t > -B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ (Table 12).

Table 12. Sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	+0	$p(A_t)$
	A_t	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(B_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Example. Sufficient condition: The combustion of a wax candle involves a chemical reaction with oxygen. The wax (a hydrocarbon) reacts with oxygen to produce carbon dioxide, water vapour, and heat. This reaction requires gaseous oxygen as a reactant, and in the presence of a sufficient amount of gaseous oxygen, the reaction proceeds, resulting in the burning of the candle. In other words, **if** there is an adequate supply of gaseous oxygen in the environment where the candle is placed, **then** the wax candle will burn. Oxygen is a key reactant in the combustion process, and its availability determines whether or not the candle can burn. Conversely, if gaseous oxygen is limited or absent, the candle will not burn, illustrating (Table 13) that the presence of gaseous oxygen is a sufficient condition for the combustion (burning) of a wax candle.

Table 13. Sufficient condition.

		Gaseous oxygen		
		is present	is not present	
Candle	is burning	1	0	1
	is not burning	1	1	2
		2	1	3

Remarkably, we can observe at this point that pilot studies with only $N=3$ Bernoulli trials may be sufficient to detect a significant relationship. This example illustrates the difference between condition and cause quite clearly. It is true that **if** the candle is burning, **then** gaseous oxygen is present. However, a burning candle is not the cause of gaseous oxygen. A cause is at the same time also a sufficient condition for a causal connection, but not vice versa. A sufficient condition does not necessarily have to be a cause. In general, a sufficient condition A_t is characterized by the property that another event B_t will occur if A_t is given, assuming A_t itself occurred (Barukčić, 1989, 2020a,b; Barukčić and Ufuoma, 2020; Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017b,c, 2020a,c), but it does not necessarily cause the same event B_t .

At this point, let's consider another aspect of the sufficient condition. The ground, the streets, the trees, human beings, and many other objects will become wet during heavy rain. Specifically, **if**

it is raining (event A_t), **then** human beings will get wet (event B_t). However, despite this common understanding, a person equipped with an appropriate umbrella (denoted by R_t) need not become wet even during heavy rain. An appropriate umbrella (R_t) can be seen as an event that counteracts the occurrence of another event (B_t) and can be understood as an **anti-event** of the event A_t or in bio-sciences something as an **anti-dot** of event A_t . In other words, an appropriate umbrella is an antidote to the effect of rain on the human body; it has the potential to protect humans from the impact of rain. Under conditions, where $p(R_t)$ has no influence on the relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, it is

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t) \equiv 1 + p(R_t) \quad (32)$$

However, it $p(R_t)$ is an antidote of A_t , it is more or less

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) + p(R_t) \equiv 1 \quad (33)$$

What could be one of the many practical consequences of this rule? Suppose a very good study A has provided evidence that

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \equiv 1 \quad (34)$$

However, a another qualitatively well-conducted study B revealed the relationship

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) < 1 \quad (35)$$

Thus far, there are good reasons to believe that in the population

$$1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) \quad (36)$$

of the second study B the antidote to the condition A_t could potentially be identified. Therefore, it may make sense to take a very close look at the population $1 - p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ of the second study B under certain circumstances. Nonetheless, and as a general rule, the following relationship

$$p((A_t) \rightarrow (B_t \wedge (\underline{R_t}))) = p((A_t) \rightarrow (B_t \wedge (\neg R_t))) \equiv (\underline{A_t} \vee (B_t \wedge (\neg R_t))) \equiv 1 \quad (37)$$

indicates to some extent that R_t is a potential antidote to A_t . However, activities such as taking a shower or swimming in a lake may also result in the human body or hair becoming wet. Nevertheless, these events do not significantly contribute to the overall outcome—the effect of rain on the human body.

2.4.8. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.9 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a sufficient condition relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about the conditio per quam relationship $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a conditio per quam relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c+d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
&\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{b^2}{A}
\end{aligned} \tag{38}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \rightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(d - (b+d))^2}{B} + \frac{((a+c) - B)^2}{B} \\
&\equiv \frac{b^2}{B} + 0 \\
&\equiv \frac{b^2}{B}
\end{aligned} \tag{39}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of the conditio per quam relationship/distribution $p(A_t \rightarrow B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis accepted. Yate's Yates (1934) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.4.9. The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship

Definition 2.10 (The left-tailed p Value of the conditio per quam relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value Barukčić (2019) of the conditio per quam relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
pValue_{lt}(A_t \rightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \rightarrow B_t))} \\
&\equiv 1 - e^{-(b/N)}
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

Again, a low P Value indicates a statistical significance.

2.4.10. Sufficient condition and risk ratio RR_{sc}

The relative risk, denoted as RR_{sc} , can potentially provide an approximate indication of the presence of a sufficient condition. **Under conditions where each trial is independent of another trial and**

where the probability of an event is constant from trial to trial it is (Barukčić, 2021c), especially under conditions of case control studies,

$$RR_{sc}(A_t, B_t) = \frac{\frac{p(a_t)}{p(B_t)}}{\frac{p(b_t)}{p(B_t)}} = \frac{p(a_t) \times p(B_t)}{p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} = \frac{N^2 \times p(a_t) \times p(B_t)}{N^2 \times p(b_t) \times p(B_t)} = \frac{a \times B}{b \times B} = +1 \quad (41)$$

For more details, see Table 2 and Table 3. It is

$$p(A_t \rightarrow B_t) = \frac{RR_{sc}(A_t, B_t) \times p(b_t) \times p(B_t)}{p(B_t)} + 1 - p(A_t) = +1 \quad (42)$$

2.4.11. Exclusion relationship

Definition 2.11 (Exclusion relationship [EXCL]).

Mathematically, the exclusion (EXCL) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t | B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t | B_t) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N (\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t)}{N} \equiv E(\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{b + c + d}{N} \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{43}$$

Based on the Henry M. Sheffer 1913 relationship, known as the Sheffer stroke (Sheffer, 1913), also known as NAND (Negation AND) function, it is $p(A_t \wedge B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t | B_t)$ (Table 14).

Table 14. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) A_t	TRUE	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

Example 2.1. *A male human being is defined as an individual characterized by the presence of reproductive organs, specifically testes, and the absence of reproductive organs such as a uterus and ovaries. Conversely, a female human being is defined as an individual characterized by the presence of reproductive organs, including a uterus and ovaries, and the absence of reproductive organs like testes. The relationship between a person's gender and pregnancy is presented in Table 15.*

Table 15. Gender and pregnancy.

		Human being		
		pregnant	not pregnant	
Human being	male	+0	$p(b_t)$	$p(A_t)$
	not male	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(\underline{A}_t)$
		$p(\underline{B}_t)$	$p(\underline{B}_t)$	+1

We cannot identify any instance of a male human being experiencing pregnancy. The attributes of being male and being pregnant are mutually exclusive. In general, only individuals assigned female at birth possess the necessary reproductive anatomy to conceive and carry a pregnancy. In biological terms, pregnancy results from fertilization, involving an egg from the ovaries and sperm from a male partner. This publication does not delve into discussions about gender beyond the binary understanding of male and female. Considerations involving transgender and non-binary individuals may lead to more complex discussions related to gender identity, gender expression, and reproductive choices. It is essential to clarify that in the above example, the term “all but male” is defined as female.

Example 2.2. Pfizer Inc. and BioNTech SE announced on Monday, November 09, 2020 - 06:45am results from a Phase 3 COVID-19 vaccine trial with 43,438 participants which provides evidence that their vaccine (BNT162b2) is preventing COVID-19 in participants without evidence of prior SARS-CoV-2 infection. In toto, 170 confirmed cases of COVID-19 were evaluated, with 8 in the vaccine group versus 162 in the placebo group (Polack et al., 2020). The data are presented as follows (Table 16).

Table 16. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) BNT162b2	TRUE	8	21712	21.720
	FALSE	162	21566	21.728
		170	43.278	43.448

The exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{Vaccine : BNT162b2} \mid \text{COVID} - 19(\text{infection})) &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - p(a_t) \\
 &\equiv 1 - \left(\frac{8}{43448} \right) \\
 &\equiv +0.999815872
 \end{aligned} \tag{44}$$

A mRNA BNT162b2 Covid-19 vaccination excludes Covid-19 (P Value = 0.000184128).

2.4.12. The goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.12 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship).

Under some well known circumstances, testing hypothesis about an exclusion relationship $p(A_t \mid B_t)$ is possible by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an exclusion relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{((c + d) - \underline{A})^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A}
 \end{aligned} \tag{45}$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t | B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{((b + d) - \underline{B})^2}{\underline{B}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + 0 \\
 &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B}
 \end{aligned} \tag{46}$$

and can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero when the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of an exclusion relationship/distribution $p(A_t | B_t)$, in which case the null hypothesis to be accepted. Yate's [Yates \(1934\)](#) continuity correction has not been used under these circumstances.

2.4.13. The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship

Definition 2.13 (The left-tailed p Value of an exclusion relationship).

It is known that as a sample size, N , increases, a sampling distribution of a special test statistic approaches the normal distribution (central limit theorem). Under these circumstances, the left-tailed (lt) p Value [Barukčić \(2019\)](#) of an exclusion relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 pValue_{\text{lt}}(A_t | B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t|B_t))} \\
 &\equiv 1 - e^{-(a/N)}
 \end{aligned} \tag{47}$$

A low P Value may provide some evidence of statistical significance.

2.4.14. Necessary and sufficient conditions

In logic and mathematics, a necessary condition is a circumstance, a factor, an event et cetera that must be present for a certain outcome, phenomenon or event to occur, while a sufficient condition is one that, if present, guarantees the occurrence of that outcome. The combination of a necessary and sufficient condition is a handy tool in the search for causality, since the same indicates that an event was present and that this event had a specific outcome. For example, in baking, the necessary condition for bread to rise is the presence of yeast (necessary), and the addition of yeast alone is a sufficient condition for bread to rise.

Definition 2.14 (Necessary and sufficient conditions [EQV]).

The necessary and sufficient condition (EQV) relationship, denoted by $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv p(a_t) + p(d_t) \\
 &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(a_t) + p(d_t))}{N} \\
 &\equiv \frac{a+d}{N} = E((A_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \wedge (\underline{A}_t \vee B_t)) \\
 &\equiv +1
 \end{aligned} \tag{48}$$

2.4.15. The Chi square goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.15 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

Even the necessary and sufficient condition relationship $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | A) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a+b))^2}{A} + \\
 &\quad \frac{d - ((c+d))^2}{\underline{A}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{b^2}{A} + \frac{c^2}{\underline{A}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{49}$$

or equally

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t | B) &\equiv \frac{(a - (a + c))^2}{B} + \\ &\frac{d - ((b + d))^2}{\underline{B}} \\ &\equiv \frac{c^2}{B} + \frac{b^2}{\underline{B}}\end{aligned}\quad (50)$$

The calculated $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be compared with a theoretical chi-square value at a certain level of significance α . Under conditions where the observed values are equal to the expected/theoretical values of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship/distribution $p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t)$, the $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution equals zero. It is to be cleared whether Yate's [Yates \(1934\)](#) continuity correction should be used at all.

2.4.16. The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship

Definition 2.16 (The left-tailed p Value of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [Barukčić \(2019\)](#) of a necessary and sufficient condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1-p(A_t \leftrightarrow B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((b+c)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (51)$$

In this context, a low P Value indicates again a statistical significance. [Table 17](#) may provide an overview of the theoretical distribution of a necessary and sufficient condition.

Table 17. Necessary and sufficient condition.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	1	0	1
	NO	0	1	1
		1	1	2

2.4.17. Necessary and sufficient condition and causation

What distinguishes [Brand and Swain \(1970, 1974\)](#); [Hilpinen \(1974\)](#); [Sanford \(1978\)](#) a (necessary and sufficient) condition from causation? This article explores the challenges in achieving precise clarity when addressing this question. In a causal relationship, excessive rain (cause) may be a factor leading to flooding (effect).

Theorem 1 (Necessary and sufficient condition and causation). *Let's consider the probabilities and independence defined by the equations:*

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = 1 \quad (52)$$

$$p(a_t) + p(b_t) = p(A_t) \quad (53)$$

$$p(a_t) + p(c_t) = p(B_t) \quad (54)$$

$$k(U_t, W_t) \equiv \frac{p(a_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t)) \times p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t))}} \quad (55)$$

We aim to prove that

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) \neq k(U_t, W_t) \quad (56)$$

Proof by contradiction. We start by assuming the opposite, i.e.,

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (57)$$

Now, let's substitute the expressions from (53) and (54) into (57):

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = (p(A_t) - p(b_t)) + (1 - p(A_t) - p(c_t)) = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (58)$$

As known (Table 2), it is $p(a_t) = (p(A_t) - p(b_t))$ and $p(d_t) = (1 - p(A_t) - p(c_t))$. In the event that the necessary and sufficient condition were identical to causality, Equation 58 would simplify, and the following relationship would be universally valid.

$$-p(b_t) - p(c_t) = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (59)$$

Let us assume that the causal relationship k is given as $k(U_t, W_t) = +1$. Equation 59 becomes,

$$-p(b_t) - p(c_t) = +1 \quad (60)$$

Under these circumstances, the necessary and sufficient condition, as given by Equation 57, is expressed as

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = +1 - p(b_t) - p(c_t) = +1. \quad (61)$$

This condition is only met if $p(b_t) = 0$ and $p(c_t) = 0$. Substituting these values and simplifying leads to a contradiction:

$$-0 = +1. \quad (62)$$

This contradiction demonstrates that the assumption in Equation 57 cannot hold, leading to the conclusion expressed in Equation 63:

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) \neq k(U_t, W_t). \quad (63)$$

Thus, it is evident that a necessary and sufficient condition is not equivalent to the causal relationship k .

□

2.4.18. Either or conditions

Definition 2.17 (Either A_t or B_t conditions [NEQV]).

Mathematically, an either A_t or B_t condition relationship (NEQV), denoted by $p(A_t >-< B_t)$ in terms of statistics and probability theory, is defined (see Barukčić, 1989, p. 68-70) as

$$\begin{aligned} p(A_t > - < B_t) &\equiv \frac{\sum_{t=1}^N ((A_t \wedge B_t) \vee (\underline{A}_t \wedge B_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv p(b_t) + p(c_t) \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times (p(b_t) + p(c_t))}{N} \\ &\equiv \frac{b + c}{N} \\ &\equiv +1 \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

It is $p(A_t > - < B_t) \equiv 1 - p(A_t < - > B_t)$ (see Table 18).

Table 18. Either A_t or B_t relationship.

		Conditioned B_t		
		YES	NO	
Condition A_t	YES	0	1	1
	NO	1	0	1
		1	1	2

2.4.19. The Chi-square goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.18 (The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship).

An either or condition relationship $p(A_t > - < B_t)$ can be tested by the chi-square distribution (also chi-squared or $\tilde{\chi}^2$ -distribution) too. The $\tilde{\chi}^2$ goodness of fit test of an either or condition relationship with degree of freedom (d. f.) of d. f. = 1 is calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | A) &\equiv \frac{(b - (a + b))^2}{A} + \frac{c - ((c + d))^2}{A} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{A} + \frac{d^2}{A}\end{aligned}\quad (65)$$

or equally as

$$\begin{aligned}\tilde{\chi}^2_{\text{Calculated}}((A_t > - < B_t) | B) &\equiv \frac{(c - (a + c))^2}{B} + \frac{b - ((b + d))^2}{B} \\ &\equiv \frac{a^2}{B} + \frac{d^2}{B}\end{aligned}\quad (66)$$

Yate's [Yates \(1934\)](#) continuity correction has not been used in this context.

2.4.20. The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship

Definition 2.19 (The left-tailed p Value of an either or condition relationship).

The left-tailed (lt) p Value [Barukčić \(2019\)](#) of an either or condition relationship can be calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}pValue_{lt}(A_t > - < B_t) &\equiv 1 - e^{-(1 - p(A_t > - < B_t))} \\ &\equiv 1 - e^{-((a+d)/N)}\end{aligned}\quad (67)$$

In this context, a low P Value indicates again a statistical significance.

2.5. Causality

2.5.1. The probability of a single event

Definition 2.20 (The probability of a single event). *The probability of a single event represents the degree of natural necessity that a specific event, ${}_R X_t$, will occur under certain circumstances. The probability of a single event is a measure between +0 and +1, where +0 indicates impossibility, and +1 indicates certainty. The relationship between a single event ${}_R X_t$, the probability of a single event $p({}_R X_t)$ and the expectation value of this single event $E({}_R X_t)$ is often expressed by the relationship*

In consideration of the definitions before, let $p({}_R X_t)$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R X_t$ at Bernoulli trial t . Let $\Psi({}_R X_t)$ represent the wavefunction, a probability amplitude (Born, 1926) of an event or of finding an event inside a set at a given (period of) time / Bernoulli trial (Uspensky, 1937) t . Let $\Psi^({}_R X_t)$ denote the complex conjugate of the wave-function. In general, it is*

$$\begin{aligned} p({}_R X_t) &\equiv p({}_R X_t) \times \frac{({}_R X_t)}{({}_R X_t)} \equiv \frac{p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t)}{({}_R X_t)} \equiv \frac{E({}_R X_t)}{{}_R X_t} \\ &\equiv p({}_R X_t) \times \frac{p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t \times {}_R X_t)}{p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t \times {}_R X_t)} \equiv \frac{p({}_R X_t) \times p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t \times {}_R X_t)}{p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t \times {}_R X_t)} \equiv \frac{E({}_R X_t)^2}{E({}_R X_t^2)} \quad (68) \\ &\equiv \Psi({}_R X_t) \times \Psi^*({}_R X_t) \end{aligned}$$

2.5.2. The n-th moment expectation value of X

Definition 2.21 (The n-th moment expectation value of X). *Let ${}_R X_t$ denote an event (at a certain (period of) time or Bernoulli trial t (Uspensky, 1937)). Let $p({}_R X_t)$ represent the probability of an event at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R X_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment **expectation value** (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Whitworth, 1901) of ${}_R X_t$. Let $E({}_R X_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_R X_t$. Let $E({}_R X_t^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of ${}_R X_t$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R X_t$** is defined as*

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R X_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R X_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^n) \times p({}_R X_t) \end{aligned} \quad (69)$$

Furthermore, it is

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R X_t^n)^m &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right)^m \times p({}_R X_t)^m \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^n)^m \times p({}_R X_t)^m \end{aligned} \quad (70)$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_R X_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R X_t^1) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1}_{(one\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R X_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^1) \times p({}_R X_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t) \times p({}_R X_t) \end{aligned} \quad (71)$$

The second moment expectation value of ${}_R X_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R X_t^2) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1}_{(two\text{-times})} \right) \times p({}_R X_t) = {}_R X_t \times ({}_R X_t \times p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^2) \times p({}_R X_t) \\ &\equiv {}_R X_t \times E({}_R X_t) \end{aligned} \quad (72)$$

2.5.3. The n-th moment expectation value of anti X

Definition 2.22 (The n-th moment expectation value of anti X). Let $p({}_R X_t)$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R X_t$ at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $(1-p({}_R X_t))$ represent the probability that a single event ${}_R X_t$ will not occur, will not exist at a given Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R \underline{X}_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value (Huygens and van Schooten, 1657; Whitworth, 1901) of anti ${}_R X_t$. Let $E({}_R \underline{X}_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R X_t$. Let $E({}_R \underline{X}_t^2)$ denote the second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R X_t$. In general, the n-th moment expectation value of anti ${}_R X_t$ is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R \underline{X}_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1 \times \dots}_{(n\text{-times})} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^n) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (73)$$

The first moment expectation value of anti ${}_R X_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E\left({}_R \underline{X}_t^1\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1}_{(one-times)} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv \left({}_R X_t^1 \right) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (74)$$

The second moment expectation value of anti ${}_R X_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E\left({}_R \underline{X}_t^2\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R X_t^1 \times {}_R X_t^1}_{(two-times)} \right) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv \left({}_R X_t^2 \right) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (75)$$

2.5.4. The n-th moment expectation value of U and W

Definition 2.23 (The n-th moment expectation value of U and W). Let $p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ represent the joint probability of an occurring of the events ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ at the same (period of time or) Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^1)$ denote the first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. In general, **the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ is defined as**

$$\begin{aligned} E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times ({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1) \times \dots}_{(n-times)} \right) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (76)$$

The first moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ follows as

$$\begin{aligned} E\left({}_R U_t^1, {}_R W_t^1\right) &\equiv \left(\underbrace{{}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1}_{(one-times)} \right) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv \left({}_R U_t^1 \times {}_R W_t^1 \right) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \\ &\equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \end{aligned} \quad (77)$$

2.5.5. The variance

Definition 2.24 (The variance). *Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890 – 1962), an English statistician, “the single most important figure in 20th century statistics” (Efron, 1998) coined the term variance as follows: “It is therefore desirable in analysing the causes of variability to deal with the square of the standard deviation as the measure of variability. We shall term this quantity the Variance ... ” (Fisher, 1918, p. 399) Again, let $p({}_R X_t)$ represent the probability of a single event ${}_R X_t$ at a given point in space-time or Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R X_t)$ denote again the expectation value of ${}_R X_t$. The expectation value of ${}_R X_t$ is defined as*

$$E({}_R X_t) \equiv p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t) \equiv \Psi({}_R X_t) \times {}_R X_t \times \Psi^*({}_R X_t) \quad (78)$$

The expectation value of the other of ${}_R X_t$, of the complementary (Barukčić, 2020a; Barukčić, 2020a) of ${}_R X_t$, of the opposite of ${}_R X_t$, of the **anti** ${}_R X_t$, denoted by ${}_R \underline{X}_t$, is defined as

$$E({}_R \underline{X}_t) \equiv (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \times ({}_R X_t) \quad (79)$$

In this context, $E({}_R X_t^2)$ is the expectation value of the second moment of ${}_R X_t$. The expectation value of ${}_R X_t^2$ is defined as

$$E({}_R X_t^2) \equiv p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t^2) \equiv p({}_R X_t) \times ({}_R X_t \times {}_R X_t) \quad (80)$$

Let $\sigma({}_R X_t)$ denote the standard deviation of ${}_R X_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R X_t)^2$ denote the variance of ${}_R X_t$. In general, the variance (Kolmogorov, 1956, p. 42) is defined (Barukčić, 2020a; Barukčić, 2020a) as

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma({}_R X_t)^2 &\equiv \sigma({}_R X_t) \times \sigma({}_R X_t) \\ &\equiv E({}_R X_t - E({}_R X_t))^2 \\ &\equiv E({}_R X_t^2) - (E({}_R X_t))^2 \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^2 \times p({}_R X_t)) - (p({}_R X_t) \times {}_R X_t)^2 \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^2) \times (p({}_R X_t) - p({}_R X_t)^2) \\ &\equiv ({}_R X_t^2) \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \\ &\equiv {}_R X_t \times (p({}_R X_t) \times {}_R X_t \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \\ &\equiv E({}_R X_t) \times {}_R X_t \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)) \\ &\equiv E({}_R X_t) \times E({}_R \underline{X}_t) \end{aligned} \quad (81)$$

Equation 81 manifests that $E({}_R X_t)$ and $E({}_R \underline{X}_t)$ are mere opposites; each is merely the negation of the other. One is not yet $E({}_R X_t)$, and the other is not yet $E({}_R \underline{X}_t)$, but both exist in opposition to each other. In this regard, each one is only insofar as the other is; its essence is derived through the other, through its own non-existence. However, each of them is only insofar as the other is not; its essence is defined through the non-existence of the other. Thus far, $E({}_R X_t)$ and $E({}_R \underline{X}_t)$ equally, represent the two sides of an opposition, constituting the implicitly determined opposition, the variance. Each of them is itself and simultaneously its other, resulting in the consequence that each has its determinateness not in another but in its own self. The other contained within each is, therefore, only insofar as its own non-being exists. The variance is a measure of the **inner contradiction** inherent in any random variable, and reaches its culmination in opposition as the unity of identity and difference.

It is self-evident that the following immediately follows from Equation 81:

$${}_R U_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \quad (82)$$

and equally that

$${}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \quad (83)$$

2.5.6. The n-th moment co-variance

Definition 2.25 (The n-th moment co-variance). Let $p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ represent the joint probability of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ at the same (period of time) Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. Let $E({}_R U_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R U_t$. Let $E({}_R W_t^n)$ denote the n-th moment expectation value of ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ denote the co-variance between ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$. In general, **the n-th moment co-variance between ${}_R U_t$ and ${}_R W_t$ is defined (Barukčić, 2020a) as**

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) &\equiv ({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\ &\equiv (({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)) - (({}_R U_t^n \times {}_R W_t^n) \times p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\ &\equiv E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) - ({}_R U_t^n \times p({}_R U_t)) \times ({}_R W_t^n \times p({}_R W_t)) \\ &\equiv E({}_R U_t^n, {}_R W_t^n) - (E({}_R U_t^n) \times E({}_R W_t^n)) \end{aligned} \quad (84)$$

From equation 84 follows equally that

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) &\equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\ &\equiv (({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t \times p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)) - (({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t))) \\ &\equiv E({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - ({}_R U_t \times p({}_R U_t)) \times ({}_R W_t \times p({}_R W_t)) \\ &\equiv E({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (E({}_R U_t) \times E({}_R W_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (85)$$

Equation 85 demands too that

$${}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))} \quad (86)$$

2.5.7. Causal relationship k

Definition 2.26 (Causal relationship k).

Nonetheless, mathematically, the causal relationship Barukčić (1989); Barukčić (1997, 2005, 2016b, 2017a,c) between a cause U_t and an effect W_t , denoted by $k(U_t, W_t)$ in terms of probability Suppes (1970) theory, is defined at each single Thompson (2006) Bernoulli trial t as

$$k(U_t, W_t) \equiv \frac{\sigma(U_t, W_t)}{\sigma(U_t) \times \sigma(W_t)} \quad (87)$$

$$\equiv \frac{p(U_t \cap W_t) - p(U_t) \times p(W_t)}{\sqrt{(p(U_t) \times (1 - p(U_t))) \times (p(W_t) \times (1 - p(W_t)))}}$$

where $\sigma(U_t, W_t)$ denotes the co-variance between a cause U_t and an effect W_t at every single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(U_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of a cause U_t at the same single Bernoulli trial t , $\sigma(W_t)$ denotes the standard deviation of an effect W_t at same single Bernoulli trial t . Table 19 provides an overview of the definition of the causal relationship k .

Table 19. The causal relationship k

		Effect W_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Cause U_t	TRUE	$p(a_t)$	$p(b_t)$	$p(U_t)$
	FALSE	$p(c_t)$	$p(d_t)$	$p(W_t)$
		$p(W_t)$	$p(W_t)$	+1

2.6. Study design

The study design is the blueprint of a research investigation, shaping its structure and methodology. It may serve as an appropriate framework for collecting, analysing, and interpreting data to answer specific research questions. The profound meaning lies in its ability to ensure the validity and reliability of study outcomes, guiding researchers in making robust inferences about the relationships they are investigating. However, the integrity of study design can be compromised through various factors, leading to biased results and undermining the scientific rigour of the research.

2.6.1. Index Of Unfairness

Definition 2.27 (Index Of Unfairness).

Bias, whether stemming from systematic errors related to study design, various factors, or random errors due to small sample sizes, can introduce imprecise conclusions, confusion, and disappointment. It may contribute to a high rate of unconfirmed or non-replicated research discoveries. This prompts the critical question: Are many of today's extensively published research findings ultimately false? **“There is increasing concern that most current published research findings are false ... Simulations show that for most study designs and settings, it is more likely for a research claim to be false than true. Moreover, for many current scientific fields, claimed research findings may often be simply accurate measures of the prevailing bias.”** (Ioannidis, 2005) Addressing this issue without discarding fundamental analytical tools poses a challenge. To mitigate bias's impact on scientific research, it becomes essential to quantify (Begg and Berlin, 1988; Begg and Mazumdar, 1994; Egger et al., 1997a,b; Higgins and Thompson, 2002; Light and Pillemer, 1984; Lin and Chu, 2018) potential biases, whether related to data collection, extraction, or publication. While accurately estimating bias remains challenging, repeated independent testing of hypotheses by diverse global investigator teams proves valuable for control and reduction. What is often overlooked is the utility of the Index of Unfairness (IOU) in this context. The IOU, yet to be fully explored (Barukčić, 2019b), provides another avenue for addressing and mitigating bias in scientific research. The index of unfairness (IOU) is defined as

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(\text{IOU}) &\equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \\
 &\equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{88}$$

where A , B and N are explained at the beginning of this publication (Table 3).

2.6.2. Index Of Independence

Definition 2.28 (Index Of Independence).

Indeed, one cannot escape the impression that studies being in line with the spirit of the present time are more likely to secure publication compared to those expressing contrary views. Considering the aforementioned and previous discussions, non-financial conflicts of interest, biases, adherence to a scientific theory, or allegiance to one's own findings may present a significant impediment to achieving a truly unbiased and equitable interpretation of scientific research. While complete exclusion of bias may be challenging, both in the short and long term, the march of scientific progress remains unstoppable and inevitable. Consequently, those endeavouring to mitigate the impact of bias on scientific research may find the index of independence (Barukčić, 2019a) to be a noteworthy focal point. The index of independence (IOI) is delineated as

$$\begin{aligned} p(\text{IOI}) &\equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \\ &\equiv \text{Absolute} \left(\left(\frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \end{aligned} \quad (89)$$

2.6.3. Placebo controlled trials

Lemma 2.1 (Placebo controlled trials). *A meticulously conducted clinical trial, employing an appropriate approach, holds paramount significance. A placebo-determined sample is one intentionally designed to lack a specific event. One notable historical example is the work of James Lind, a Scottish naval surgeon, in the mid-18th century. Lind (Lind, 1753) conducted what is often considered one of the first clinical trials in medical history to investigate the impact of various treatments on Vitamin C deficiency, known as scurvy. The value of placebo-controlled clinical trials is particularly noteworthy for standard investigations into various relationships. In this experimental design, a sample experimental group (A_t), wherein an event is present (allocated blindly or randomly, etc.)—referred to as the **verum group**—can be compared to another **placebo group** ($\underline{A}$), which specifically lacks this particular event, during **the same (period of) time or Bernoulli trial t**. To ensure optimal and reproducible results, investigators often strive to maintain the condition $A \equiv \underline{A}$. Under these circumstances, it is evident that*

$$p(\text{IOU}) \equiv p(\text{IOI}) \quad (90)$$

Direct proof. Sometimes, placebo-controlled (double-blind) trials are grounded on the demand that

$$A \equiv \underline{A} \quad (91)$$

Adding B, it is

$$A + B \equiv \underline{A} + B \quad (92)$$

Dividing by N, we obtain

$$\frac{A+B}{N} \equiv \frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} \quad (93)$$

Rearranging, it is

$$\frac{A+B}{N} - 1 \equiv \frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} - 1 \quad (94)$$

Taking the absolute, it is

$$Absolute \left(\left(\frac{A+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \equiv Absolute \left(\left(\frac{\underline{A}+B}{N} \right) - 1 \right) \quad (95)$$

and finally

$$p(IOU) \equiv p(IOI) \quad (96)$$

□

The history of scientific research underscores the significance of sample size calculation in conducting thorough investigations and statistical analyses. Generally, a small sample size may result in reduced statistical power, diminishing the likelihood of research findings being accurate. However, even studies with smaller sample sizes can effectively unveil relationships present within a population. The quality of data obtained from a study appears to hold greater importance than the study's sample size. In this context, it's crucial to note that studies grounded on the condition $p(IOU) \equiv p(IOI)$ do not automatically guarantee scientifically validated knowledge, and complete exclusion of systematic bias is not assured. On the contrary, such studies can lead to incorrect results, involve significant costs, and are, furthermore, highly labour, capital, and time-consuming, ultimately hindering progress.

Theorem 2 (Exclusion Relationship and Placebo Controlled Trials). *Claim:* Under conditions where the study design demands that $A \equiv \underline{A}$, the probability of an exclusion relationship is given as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv \frac{2 \times b}{N} \quad (97)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. Under conditions of placebo-controlled trials, it is demanded that the study design satisfies

$$A \equiv \underline{A} \quad (98)$$

Adding b to this relationship, we obtain

$$b + A \equiv b + \underline{A} \quad (99)$$

which is equivalent to the exclusion relationship

$$b + A \equiv b + \underline{A} \equiv N \times E(\underline{A}_t \vee \underline{B}_t) \equiv N \equiv \text{EXCL} \quad (100)$$

However, if an exclusion relationship is given, it is at the same time $b = A$. We obtain

$$b + b \equiv 2 \times b \equiv N \quad (101)$$

Under conditions where the study design that $A \equiv \underline{A}$, the probability of an exclusion relationship is given as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv \frac{2 \times b}{N} \quad (102)$$

□

Taking again the data of the study of Polack et al. (Polack et al., 2020), we obtain the following table (Table 20).

Table 20. A_t excludes B_t and vice versa.

		Conditioned (COVID-19) B_t		
		TRUE	FALSE	
Condition (Vaccine) BNT162b2	TRUE	8	21712	21.720
	FALSE	162	21566	21.728
		170	43.278	43.448

The probability of the exclusion relationship is calculated as

$$p(A_t | B_t) \equiv \frac{2 \times b}{N} \equiv \frac{2 \times 21712}{43448} \equiv 0.9994476155 \quad (103)$$

The P Value is about 5.523844596/10000 or 0.0005523844596 in contrast to the originally calculated P Value of 0.000184128. The study design of placebo controlled trials with the demand that $A \equiv \underline{A}$ results at the end in a higher P Value than the true underlying P Value. In other words, the study may fail to detect a significant effect that actually exists, leading to a potential Type II error. In a one-sided hypothesis test, the P Value represents the probability of observing a test statistic as extreme as the one obtained, assuming the null hypothesis is true. In contrast, a two-sided hypothesis test considers extreme values in both tails of the distribution. The P Value in a two-sided test is typically twice the P Value in a one-sided test because it accounts for extreme values in both directions. Therefore, a P Value that is considered significant in a one-sided test would still be considered significant in a two-sided test, but the reverse may not be true. The demand that $A \equiv \underline{A}$ appears to be more appropriate for a two-sided test. For a left-tailed one-sided test, it should be considered to demand that $b \equiv c$, while for a right-tailed one-sided test the demand that $a \equiv d$ appears to be more suitable.

2.6.4. Exclusion relationship and P Value

Fisher's contributions to statistics include the development of the null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis framework (Fisher, 1925) as part of his broader efforts to establish a systematic and rigorous approach to experimental design and statistical inference.

The null hypothesis (H_0) typically represents a statement of no effect or no difference, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) posits the presence of an effect or difference. In scientific research, data are collected, and researchers conduct various types of statistical tests to ascertain whether there is sufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis. The null hypothesis serves as the default assumption to be tested against the alternative hypothesis. The null hypothesis in this context would typically be that there is no exclusion relationship within the population, or $E(A_t | B_t) < N$. The alternative hypothesis asserts the presence of a relationship $E(A_t | B_t) = N$ within the population. In general, it is:

Null hypothesis: $H_0 : E(A_t | B_t) < N$

Alternative hypothesis: $H_1 : E(A_t | B_t) = (p(A_t | B_t) = 1) \times N = N$

In more detail, what is the evidence against a null hypothesis? The level of significance level, α , is the threshold used to determine statistical significance. Common choices are 0.05 or 0.01. The P Value (Arbutnot, John, 1710; Barukčić, 2019; Fisher, 1925; Pearson, 1900; Venn, 1888) assesses the strength of evidence against the null hypothesis but does not provide the probability of the null hypothesis being true. Under circumstances, where the P Value is less than or equal to α , the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. A small P Value (usually less than 0.05) suggests that the observed data is unlikely to have occurred by random chance alone, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis in favour of the alternative hypothesis.

Theorem 3 (Exclusion relationship and P Value). *The P Value for a left-tailed test is determined by the cumulative probability up to the observed value. In general, it is*

$$P \text{ Value (one sided left tailed)} = P(X \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(X = N) = 1 - p(A_t | B_t) \quad (104)$$

Proof by direct proof. Consider a random variable X with a probability mass function (PMF) for discrete distributions, $p(X = x)$. The cumulative distribution function $F(x)$ is defined as:

$$F(x) = p(X = 0) + p(X = 1) + \dots + p(X = N - 1) + p(X = N) \quad (105)$$

The cumulative distribution function $F(x)$ should satisfy the condition that the probability of any value up to x is 1. If N Bernoulli trials are performed, it is

$$F(x) = p(X = 0) + p(X = 1) + \dots + p(X = N - 1) + p(X = N) = +1 \quad (106)$$

This equation states that the cumulative probability of observing any value less than or equal to N is the sum of the probabilities of each individual measurement or event up to N . The sum of these probabilities should be equal to 1, which is a fundamental property of probability distributions. This principle holds true for the exclusion relationship as well. Theoretically, the exclusion relationship need to be given at any run of a Bernoulli trial. Thus far, it is worth acknowledging that

$$P(X \leq N - 1) = p(X = 0) + p(X = 1) + \dots + p(X = N - 1) \quad (107)$$

In other words, the cumulative distribution function is given as

$$F(x) = P(X \leq N - 1) + p(X = N) = +1 \quad (108)$$

Therefore, it is

$$P(X \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(X = N) \quad (109)$$

As generally known, the cumulative distribution function (CDF) is related to the calculation of the P Value, especially in the context of hypothesis testing. The P Value itself is associated with a specific observed test statistic in hypothesis testing. For a one-tailed test, the P Value is the probability of observing a test statistic as extreme as, or more extreme than, the one observed, assuming the null hypothesis is true. In general, for a left-tailed test, the P Value is typically calculated as $P(X \leq \text{observed value})$, which corresponds to the cumulative probability up to the observed value. In other words, the P Value of a left-tailed test is equivalent to $F(\text{observed value})$. The P Value for a left-tailed test is determined by the cumulative probability up to the observed value. In general, it is (Barukčić, 2019)

$$\text{P Value (one sided left tailed)} = P(X \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(X = N) \quad (110)$$

In summary, $p(X \leq N - 1)$ is related to the left-tailed cumulative distribution function, and it is commonly used as the P Value in hypothesis testing for a left-tailed test of an exclusion relationship. □

As demonstrated before (Table 16), it is

$$p(X = N) = p(A_t | B_t) = 0.999815872 \quad (111)$$

and the P Value is given as

$$\text{P Value} = P(X \leq N - 1) = 1 - p(X = N) = 1 - p(A_t | B_t) = 1 - 0.999815872 = 0.000184128 \quad (112)$$

which is a highly significant result. We reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis. A vaccination with BNT162b2 (Polack et al., 2020) excludes COVID-19 (P Value = 0.0005523844596).

3. Results

3.1. Superposition principle

The superposition principle asserts that the expected value of the sum of N random variables is equal to the sum of their individual expected values. This property holds true even when the random variables are not independent. Originating as far back as Steno's work in 1669 (Stenonis, Nicolai, 1669), the superposition principle stands as a fundamental concept (Brillouin, Leon, 1946, p. 21) in science. Notably, the decomposition of functions into trigonometric series, introduced by Fourier in 1822 (Fourier, 1822), has been a pivotal development for linear systems and the principle of superposition. Today, the superposition principle is one of the fundamental principles of quantum mechanics (Schrödinger, Erwin Rudolf Josef Alexander, 1926) and explains how a quantum state, indicated i.e. by $E(X)_t$, can be represented as the sum of two or more (eigen-) states ($E(X_i)_t$). The principle of superposition simplifies the calculation of expected values in probability theory and statistics, offering a straightforward approach to handling the expected values of combinations of random variables, which is of great significance in the context of this publication.

Theorem 4 (Superposition Principle). *Claim: It is*

$$E(X) = E\left(\sum_{i=1}^N X_i\right) = \sum_{i=1}^N E(X_i) \quad (113)$$

where $E(X)$ represents the expected value or average value of a single random variable.

Proof by induction. Basis Step (Induction): For $N = 1$, we have:

$$E\left(\sum_{i=1}^1 X_i\right) = E\left(\sum_{i=1}^1 X_i\right) \quad (114)$$

which holds true.

Inductive Step: Assume the claim is true for $N = k$. Now, we want to show it for $N = k + 1$:

$$E\left(\sum_{i=1}^{k+1} X_i\right) = E\left(\sum_{i=1}^k X_i + X_{k+1}\right) = E\left(\sum_{i=1}^k X_i\right) + E(X_{k+1}) = \sum_{i=1}^k E(X_i) + E(X_{k+1}) \quad (115)$$

Thus, the claim holds for $N = k + 1$ as well.

By mathematical induction, the claim is proven. $\square$

This principle holds true especially at one run of an experiment, i.e.

$$E(X)_t = \left(\sum_{i=1}^N E(X_i)\right)_t = E\left(\sum_{i=1}^N X_i\right)_t$$

Example

The sample space (Ω) for a fair six-sided die represents all possible outcomes even before a roll of a die, including outcomes of those from multiple trials. The sample space (Ω) for a single trial of a fair six-sided die, especially before an act of measurement, is given as:

$$\Omega = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$$

However, for N trials, the sample space (Ω) would be the set of all possible sequences of outcomes, such as

$$\Omega = \{1, 3, 2, 4, 6, \dots\}$$

where each number in the sequence corresponds to the outcome of a single trial. The event space ($\mathcal{F}$) is the set of all possible subsets of the sample space, including the empty set and the sample space itself:

$$\mathcal{F} = 2^\Omega$$

As next, we consider an act of measurement, a fair six-sided die is rolled. Again, let X denote the random variable representing the outcome of the fair six-sided die before any roll (i.e., the initial state) or at a single roll. The expectation value ($E(X)$) is calculated as:

$$E(X) = \frac{1}{6} \times 1 + \frac{1}{6} \times 2 + \frac{1}{6} \times 3 + \frac{1}{6} \times 4 + \frac{1}{6} \times 5 + \frac{1}{6} \times 6 \quad (116)$$

Simplifying this expression gives:

$$E(X) = \frac{21}{6} = 3.5 \quad (117)$$

Therefore, before the roll is performed, the expectation value of the fair six-sided die exists in the state of superposition of individual states and is given by 3.5. This represents the average value expected over many repetitions, considering all possible outcomes with their respective probabilities. Now, introduce the notation $E(\bar{X}) = \frac{E(X)}{N}$. This expression represents the average value obtained over N independent trials of the initial state, where each trial contributes $\frac{E(X)}{N}$ to the sum. In mathematical terms:

$$\begin{aligned} N \times \frac{E(X)}{N} &= N \times E\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N X_i}{N}\right) \\ &= N \times E(\bar{X}) = E(X) \end{aligned} \quad (118)$$

This equation illustrates that the sum of the expected values over N trials, each scaled by $\frac{1}{N}$, equals the overall expected value. This is a fundamental relationship between expectation values and averages. So, when we talk about $N \times \frac{E(X)}{N}$, it is indeed related to the average value, and as N approaches infinity, this expression converges to $E(X)$, reflecting the expected value over many repetitions of the initial state.

The relationship between the wave function and eigenfunctions lies in the fact that the wave function, which represents the quantum state of a physical system, can be decomposed into a sum of eigenfunctions, and the coefficients of this sum determine the probability amplitudes associated with different eigenstates of the system. In general, it is

$$E(X)_t = E(X_1)_t + E(X_2)_t + E(X_3)_t + \dots \quad (119)$$

Multiplying equation before by an unknown parameter y , it is

$$E(X)_t \times y = E(X_1)_t \times y + E(X_2)_t \times y + E(X_3)_t \times y + \dots \quad (120)$$

In our understanding, it is $y = \frac{1}{X \times \Psi^*}$ and we obtain

$$\underbrace{\Psi = E(X)_t \times \frac{1}{X \times \Psi^*}}_{\dots \text{wave function} \dots} = \underbrace{\left(\frac{E(X_1)_t}{X \times \Psi^*} \right) + \left(\frac{E(X_2)_t}{X \times \Psi^*} \right) + \left(\frac{E(X_3)_t}{X \times \Psi^*} \right) + \dots}_{\dots \text{eigen functions} \dots} \quad (121)$$

3.2. The variance of a binomial distributed random variable

The term “binomial ” has a rich history in science, first demonstrably used in 1557 in “The Whetstone of Witte ” by Robert Recorde (Recorde, 1557). Jacob Bernoulli, in his 1713 work “Ars Conjectandi ” (Bernoulli, 1713, p. 45), discovered one of the oldest known probability distributions, the binomial distribution. A few years later, in 1718, Abraham De Moivre discussed the “coefficients of the binomial ” (Moivre, 1718). The binomial distribution proves particularly useful when there are exactly two mutually exclusive outcomes of a trial (Birnbaum, 1961, p. 417). In the course of scientific development, Karl Pearson proposed a method to define the standard deviation of a binomial distribution, stating:

“... the mean square error for any binomial distribution ... is identical with the value $\sqrt{npq}$ ” (Pearson, 1895, p. 351).

With this definition, Karl Pearson approached a solution to the issue, but narrowly missed achieving a definitive resolution. Meanwhile, Pearson’s definition of the standard deviation for a binomial distribution has been widely acknowledged, although a proof supporting this definition has not explicitly been presented by Pearson. Due to the widespread acceptance of Pearson’s definition of the standard deviation for the binomial distribution, there has been a kind of shift in the burden of proof for its correctness. Pearson, who would typically have had the burden to prove the validity of his claim, understandably no longer bears this responsibility, and others must provide evidence for the correctness of his assertion. This type of scientific “burden of proof reversal ” is particularly challenging for those who still harbour justified doubts about the validity of Pearson’s definition.

Theorem 5 (Variance in general). *According to Equation 81, the variance (Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933, p. 38) of a random variable is given as*

$$\sigma_{(RX_t)}^2 = E(RX_t^2) - (E(RX_t))^2 = RX_t^2 \times (p(RX_t) \times (1 - p(RX_t))) \quad (122)$$

Direct proof. In general, it is

$$1 = 1 \quad (123)$$

or

$$1 + 0 = 1 \quad (124)$$

and

$$p(RX_t) + 1 - p(RX_t) = 1 \quad (125)$$

Equation 125 becomes

$$\frac{(RX_t)^2 \times (p(RX_t))^2}{(RX_t)^2 \times (p(RX_t))} + 1 - \frac{(RX_t)^2 \times (p(RX_t))^2}{(RX_t)^2 \times (p(RX_t))} = 1 \quad (126)$$

Simplifying Equation 126, we obtain

$$\frac{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2}{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))} + \frac{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))}{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))} - \frac{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2}{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))} = 1 \quad (127)$$

Equation 127 simplifies as

$$\frac{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 + \left((\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) \right) - (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2}{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))} = 1 \quad (128)$$

Equation 72 demands that $E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) = (\mathbb{R}X_t^2) \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))$. Equation 128 becomes

$$\frac{(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 + \left((\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) \right) - (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2}{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)} = 1 \quad (129)$$

Equation 71 demands that $E(\mathbb{R}X_t) = (\mathbb{R}X_t) \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))$. Equation 129 becomes

$$\frac{(E(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 + \left((\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) \right) - (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2}{E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2)} = 1 \quad (130)$$

Rearranging Equation 130, it is

$$(E(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 + \left((\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) \right) - (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 = E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) \quad (131)$$

and

$$+ \left((\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) \right) - (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 = E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) - (E(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 = \sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \quad (132)$$

or

$$\sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 = E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) - (E(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 = +(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times \left((p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) - (p(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 \right) \quad (133)$$

Simplifying Equation 133 results in the general form of the variance, which is independent of any distribution. In general, the variance of a random variable (Barukčić, 2023, pp. 22-23), regardless of the distribution, is expressed as:

$$\sigma(\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 = E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) - (E(\mathbb{R}X_t))^2 = (\mathbb{R}X_t)^2 \times p(\mathbb{R}X_t) \times (1 - p(\mathbb{R}X_t)) = E(\mathbb{R}X_t) \times E(\mathbb{R}\underline{X}_t) \quad (134)$$

□

Based on Theorem 4, Equation 134 can be generalized further as

$$\sigma(\mathbb{R}X)^2 = E(\mathbb{R}X_t^2) - (E(\mathbb{R}X))^2 = (\mathbb{R}X)^2 \times p(\mathbb{R}X) \times (1 - p(\mathbb{R}X)) \quad (135)$$

At this point, we would like to express the variance of a random variable using multiplication.

Theorem 6 (Variance as the unity and the struggle between X and Anti X). *In general, the expectation value of the other, complementary, or opposite of X, denoted as $E(\underline{R}X_t)$, is given as*

$$E(\underline{R}X_t) = RX_t \times (1 - p(RX_t)) \quad (136)$$

Direct proof. The following equation is intended to be universally applicable and independent of any distribution of a random variable. According to Equation 134, it is

$$\sigma(RX_t)^2 = E(RX_t^2) - (E(RX_t))^2 = E(RX_t) \times E(\underline{R}X_t) \quad (137)$$

What are the immediate and undeniable consequences of such an assumption? Equation 137 changes slightly to

$$\sigma(RX_t)^2 = E(RX_t^2) - (E(RX_t))^2 = (RX_t \times E(\underline{R}X_t)) - (E(RX_t))^2 = E(RX_t) \times E(\underline{R}X_t) \quad (138)$$

in accordance with Equation 72. We obtain

$$(RX_t \times E(\underline{R}X_t)) - (E(RX_t))^2 = E(RX_t) \times (RX_t - E(RX_t)) = E(RX_t) \times E(\underline{R}X_t) \quad (139)$$

where $E(\underline{R}X_t)$ is the other of the something, the complementary, the local hidden variable, the opposing, etc. Equation 139 is divided by $E(RX_t)$ and becomes

$$(RX_t - E(RX_t)) = E(\underline{R}X_t) \quad (140)$$

Equation 71 demands that $E(RX_t) = (RX_t) \times (p(RX_t))$. Equation 140 becomes

$$(RX_t) - (RX_t \times p(RX_t)) = RX_t \times (1 - p(RX_t)) = E(\underline{R}X_t) \quad (141)$$

In general, the expectation value of the other, the complementary, or the opposite of X, denoted as $E(\underline{R}X_t)$, is given as

$$E(\underline{R}X_t) = RX_t \times (1 - p(RX_t)) \quad (142)$$

□

In general, it is,

$$\sigma(RX_t)^2 = E(RX_t) \times E(\underline{R}X_t) \leq \left(\frac{(RX_t)^2}{4} = \frac{\pi \times \hbar \times (RX_t)^2}{2 \times h} \right) \quad (143)$$

while $\frac{\pi \times \hbar}{2 \times h} \equiv \frac{1}{4}$ and $RX_t \geq 2 \times \sigma(RX_t)$. Find proof of this somewhere else in literature.

Theorem 7 (The variance of a binomial random variable). *The variance of a binomial random variable is given as*

$$\sigma(RX_t)^2 = RX_t^2 \times (p(RX_t) \times (1 - p(RX_t))) = N \times N \times (p(RX_t) \times (1 - p(RX_t))) \quad (144)$$

Direct proof. In general, the variance of a random variable is defined as

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = E({}_R X_t^2) - (E({}_R X_t))^2 = E({}_R X_t) \times E({}_R \underline{X}_t) = {}_R X_t^2 \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \quad (145)$$

Under the condition of a binomial distribution, the expected value of X_t is given as $E({}_R X_t) = {}_R X_t \times p({}_R X_t) = N \times p({}_R X_t)$ while the probability $p({}_R X_t)$ is constant from trial to trial. Equation 145 becomes

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = (N \times p({}_R X_t)) \times E({}_R \underline{X}_t) = {}_R X_t^2 \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \quad (146)$$

In accordance with the previously proven and derived Equation 142 it is $E({}_R \underline{X}_t) = {}_R X_t \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))$. Equation 146 changes to

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = (N \times p({}_R X_t)) \times ({}_R X_t \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) = {}_R X_t^2 \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \quad (147)$$

Simplifying Equation 147, we obtain

$$(N \times {}_R X_t) = {}_R X_t^2 \quad (148)$$

Under conditions of a binomial distributed random variable it is

$$N = {}_R X_t \quad (149)$$

Based on the insight of Equation 149, we obtain the variance of the binomial distributed random variable as

$$\sigma({}_R X_t)^2 = {}_R X_t^2 \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) = N \times N \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t))) \quad (150)$$

□

The standard deviation of a Bernoulli distributed random variable is given as

$$\sigma({}_R X_t) = \sqrt{{}_R X_t^2 \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)))} = \sqrt{N \times N \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)))} \quad (151)$$

and not as

$$\sigma({}_R X_t) = \sqrt{N \times (p({}_R X_t) \times (1 - p({}_R X_t)))} \quad (152)$$

as claimed by Pearson (Pearson, 1895, p. 351).

3.3. The covariance of two binomially distributed random variables

The covariance of two binomially distributed random variables, denoted as, $Cov(U_t, W_t)$ measures how much the values of one variable (U_t) tend to vary with the values of the other variable (W_t).

Theorem 8 (The covariance of two binomially distributed random variables). *The covariance of two binomially distributed random variables can be expressed as follows:*

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - E(U) \times E(W) = N \times N \times (p(U \times W)) - (p(U) \times p(W)) \quad (153)$$

Proof. In general, covariance is defined as

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - E(U) \times E(W) \quad (154)$$

Under the conditions of a binomial distribution with parameters $(N, p(U_t))$ and $(N, p(W_t))$ for U_t and W_t respectively, it becomes

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - ((N \times p(U_t)) \times (N \times p(W_t))) \quad (155)$$

where N is the sample or population's size and $p(U_t)$ and $p(W_t)$ is the single probability which is constant from trial to trial. Further, assuming independence, we obtain:

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - ((N \times p(U_t)) \times (N \times p(W_t))) = 0 \quad (156)$$

In other words, under conditions of a binomial distribution, we obtain

$$E(U, W) = (N \times p(U) \times N \times p(W)) \quad (157)$$

In other words, under conditions of a binomial distribution, it is given:

$$E(U, W) = X \times p(U, W) = (N \times p(U) \times N \times p(W)) \quad (158)$$

Under conditions of independence, it is

$$p(U, W) = p(U) \times p(W) \quad (159)$$

Equation before changes to

$$X \times p(U, W) = N \times N \times p(U) \times p(W) = N \times N \times p(U, W) \quad (160)$$

At the end, the value of X follows as

$$X = N \times N \quad (161)$$

The covariance of binomial distributed random variable is given as

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - E(U) \times E(W) = (X \times p(U \times W)) - (E(U) \times E(W)) \quad (162)$$

or as

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - E(U) \times E(W) = (N \times N \times p(U \times W)) - (N \times p(U) \times N \times p(W)) \quad (163)$$

The covariance of binomial distributed random variables is given as

$$Cov(U, W) = E(U \times W) - E(U) \times E(W) = N \times N \times (p(U \times W)) - (p(U) \times p(W)) \quad (164)$$

□

3.4. Relative frequency and probability

Very often, we work with relative frequencies rather than individual probabilities. Various authors have pointed out the possibility of the identity of relative frequency with individual probability. Venn himself writes, among other things: “probability is nothing but that proportion” (Venn, 1888, p. 84). It is therefore necessary and helpful to refer to the identity and difference between relative frequency and individual probability. A proof by contradiction is a proof technique where we begin by assuming the negation of the statement we aim to prove. Subsequently, we demonstrate that this initial assumption inevitably leads to a logical contradiction. By revealing that our assumption, contrary to our intended claim, results in a logical inconsistency, we logically establish the validity of the original statement.

Theorem 9. *The probability of a single event, denoted as $p(X_t)$ and the relative frequency of a single event, denoted as, $n(X_t)$ are not identical. In general, it is*

$$p(X_t) \neq n(X_t) \quad (165)$$

Proof by Contradiction.

First step. Assumption (Negation): We assume, that the negation of the statement we want to prove, is true. Therefore, we suppose that the probability of a single event is identical to its relative frequency. In general, including every single trial t , it is

$$p(X_t) = n(X_t) \quad (166)$$

Second step. Logical Deduction: At this stage, we are applying logical rules, properties, or known theorems to explore the implications of the negation assumed before to derive some consequences of the assumption before. For this reason, we conduct a theoretical thought experiment and toss a fair coin. The probability of a single event is $p(X_t) = \frac{1}{2}$. The relative frequency that heads were tossed is determined by the absolute frequency ($H(X)$) with which heads occurred, divided by the number of tosses X or in other words: $n(X_t) = \frac{H(X)}{X}$ According to our assumption:

$$p(X_t) = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{H(X)}{X} = n(X_t) \quad (167)$$

Now, let us consider a specific case where $X = N = 1$ where we obtained head ($H(X) = 1$). It is

$$p(X_t) = \frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{1} = n(X_t) \quad (168)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{2} = \frac{1}{1} \quad (169)$$

or

$$1 = 2 \quad (170)$$

Third step. Reach a Contradiction: Finally, the consequences of our assumption above lead to a logical contradiction:

$$0 = 1 \quad (171)$$

Fourth step. Conclude the Original Statement: Nonetheless, a contradiction is something that is known to be false or that violates fundamental logical or mathematical principles. However, either $p(X_t) = n(X_t)$ is true or $p(X_t) \neq n(X_t)$ is not true. Since assuming the negation of our theorem led to a contradiction, we are logically entitled to conclude that the negation $p(X_t) = n(X_t)$ is not true and that the original statement $p(X_t) \neq n(X_t)$ must be true. The probability of a single event is not identical with the relative frequency. $\square$

3.5. Relative frequency and probability

Theorem 10. For the given definitions:

$$H(X_t) = n(X_t) \times X_t \quad (172)$$

and

$$E(X_t) = p(X_t) \times X_t \quad (173)$$

we aim to prove that

$$n(X_t) = \left(\frac{H(X_t)}{E(X_t)} \right) \times p(X_t) \quad (174)$$

Proof by induction. **Base Case:** For $X = 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LHS: } n(1) &= \left(\frac{H(1)}{E(1)} \right) \times p(1) \\ &= \left(\frac{n(1) \times 1}{p(1) \times 1} \right) \times p(1) \\ &= n(1) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the base case holds.

Inductive Step: Assume the theorem holds for $X = k$, i.e.,

$$n(k) = \left(\frac{H(k)}{E(k)} \right) \times p(k) \quad (175)$$

Now, consider $X = k + 1$:

$$\text{LHS: } n(k+1) = \left(\frac{H(k+1)}{E(k+1)} \right) \times p(k+1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \left(\frac{n(k+1) \times (k+1)}{p(k+1) \times (k+1)} \right) \times p(k+1) \\
&= n(k+1)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the theorem is proven by mathematical induction.

□

Von Mises discusses the possibility that the probability of an event can be understood as the limit of the relative frequency of its occurrence (von Mises, 1927, p. 497). In his explanation, he states that, “... Wahrscheinlichkeit eines Ereignisses als Grenzwert der relativen Häufigkeit seines Auftretens ...” (von Mises, 1927, p. 497) Translated into English: ‘... probability of an event as the limit of the relative frequency of its occurrence ...’. Following von Mises, mathematically, the probability of an event as the limit of the relative frequency would be given as follows:

$$p(A_t) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\text{Number of occurrences of } A_t}{\text{Total number of trials } N} = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} n(A_t) \quad (176)$$

where $p(A_t)$ is the probability of event A_t , N is the number of trials, and $n(A_t)$ is the relative frequency of A_t after N trials. In other words, “... the relative frequency ... is the ratio of the number of cases ... found to the total number of observations.” (Mises, 1957, p. 14). As a reason for this, von Mises states: “Die relative Häufigkeit, mit der ein Ereignis auftritt, nähert sich bei andauernder Fortsetzung der Versuche immer mehr einem festen Wert.” (von Mises, 1927, p. 497) Translated into English: ‘The relative frequency with which an event occurs approaches a fixed value with the ongoing continuation of experiments.’ Von Mises provides a clear answer regarding what this fixed value represents: “... the relative frequency of the observed ... tend to a fixed limit ... This limit will be called the probability” (Mises, 1957, p. 15). However, as demonstrated previously (Theorem 10), this concept requires a more nuanced consideration. We must consider at this point that a different perspective on this issue given as

$$p(A_t) = \left(\lim_{H(A_t) \rightarrow E(A_t)} \frac{\text{Expection value: } E(A_t)}{\text{Absolute value: } H(A_t)} \right) \times n(A_t) = n(A_t) \quad (177)$$

where $p(A_t)$ is the probability of event A_t , $H(A_t)$ is the absolute (frequency) value of A_t , $E(A_t)$ is the expectation value of A_t and $n(A_t)$ is the relative frequency of A_t may be more insightful.

3.6. The identity of Conjunction and Multiplication: $A_t \wedge B_t = A_t \times B_t$

Theorem 11 (Conjunction and Multiplication). *For any events A_t and B_t or propositions, it holds (Table 21) that*

Table 21. Conjunction ($\wedge$) and Multiplication ($\times$)

Bernoulli trial t	A_t	B_t	$A_t \wedge B_t$	$A_t \times B_t$
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0	0
3	0	1	0	0
4	0	0	0	0
...	...	...	...	...

or more formally:

$$(A_t \wedge B_t) = (A_t \times B_t) \quad (178)$$

Proof by induction. We will prove this equation by induction on the variable t .

Base Case ($t = 1$):

Assume A_1 is true and B_1 is true. Then,

$$A_1 \wedge B_1 = A_1 \times B_1 = 1 \wedge 1 = 1 \times 1 = 1 \quad (179)$$

Base Case ($t = 2$):

Assume A_1 is true and B_1 is false. Then,

$$A_1 \wedge B_1 = A_1 \times B_1 = 1 \wedge 0 = 1 \times 0 = 0 \quad (180)$$

Base Case ($t = 3$):

Assume A_1 is false and B_1 is true. Then,

$$A_1 \wedge B_1 = A_1 \times B_1 = 0 \wedge 1 = 0 \times 1 = 0 \quad (181)$$

Base Case ($t = 3$):

Assume A_1 is false and B_1 is false. Then,

$$A_1 \wedge B_1 = A_1 \times B_1 = 0 \wedge 0 = 0 \times 0 = 0 \quad (182)$$

Inductive Step:

Assume the proposition holds for $t = k$, i.e., $A_k \wedge B_k = A_k \times B_k$.

Now, we want to show it holds for $t = k + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned} A_{k+1} \wedge B_{k+1} &= A_{k+1} \times B_{k+1} \\ (A_k \wedge B_k) \wedge (A_{k+1} \wedge B_{k+1}) &= (A_k \times B_k) \times (A_{k+1} \times B_{k+1}) \\ A_k \wedge B_k \wedge A_{k+1} \wedge B_{k+1} &= A_k \times B_k \times A_{k+1} \times B_{k+1} \end{aligned}$$

This completes the inductive step.

By mathematical induction, the proposition holds for all t .

□

As can be observed, the table (Table 21) already provides a comprehensive proof of the matter. The definitions are discernible from the table, involving 0/1 random variables, and so forth. The table serves as evidence significantly more intelligible than a conventional proof. Therefore, it is often entirely sufficient to present such a table (Table 21) as proof.

3.7. Necessary and sufficient condition

Theorem 12 (Necessary and sufficient condition). *Let us define $(U_t) = (W_t) = 1$, otherwise, $(U_t) \neq (W_t) = 0$. A necessary and sufficient condition between (U_t) and (W_t) demands in general that*

$$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) = (U_t = W_t) \quad (183)$$

Proof. We want to prove that,

$$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) = (U_t = W_t) \quad (184)$$

Let us break down this equality into various parts, as demonstrated (Table 22).

Table 22. Necessary and sufficient condition between (U_t) and (W_t)

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$	$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t))$	$((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)$	$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t))$	$U_t = W_t$
1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
3	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
4	0	0	0	1	1	1	1
...	...	...	...	...	...	...	...

Therefore, we have shown that

$$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) = (U_t = W_t) \quad (185)$$

□

3.8. Conjunction and (Necessary and Sufficient) Condition

As demonstrated before (Table 22), it is,

$$A_t \wedge B_t \neq ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (186)$$

However, such a proof can be done in a more formal way.

Theorem 13 (Conjunction and (Necessary and Sufficient) Condition). *In general, for any propositions A_t and B_t , it is*

$$A_t \wedge B_t \neq ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (187)$$

Proof. We will prove the theorem by contradiction. Assume, for the sake of contradiction, that

$$A_t \wedge B_t = ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (188)$$

Now, let's use logical equivalence and distributive properties step by step.

Logical equivalence allows us to replace a subexpression with an equivalent expression. For example:

$$A \equiv (A \wedge B) \vee (A \wedge \neg B) \quad (189)$$

Now, let's apply this principle to the equation:

$$\begin{aligned} A_t &\equiv ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \\ &\equiv ((A_t \wedge \neg A_t) \vee (A_t \wedge B_t) \vee (\neg B_t \wedge \neg A_t) \vee (\neg B_t \wedge B_t)) \end{aligned} \quad (190)$$

In the above step, we applied logical equivalence to each part of the conjunction.

Next, we use distributive properties:

$$\begin{aligned} &\equiv (0 \vee (A_t \wedge B_t) \vee 0 \vee 0) \\ &\equiv A_t \wedge B_t \end{aligned} \quad (191)$$

This simplification is based on the fact that $0 \vee X \equiv X$.

However, this implies $A_t = 0$ or $B_t = 1$, which contradicts the assumption that

$$A_t \wedge B_t = ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (192)$$

Therefore, our assumption that

$$A_t \wedge B_t = ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (193)$$

must be false. Hence, the original statement holds:

$$A_t \wedge B_t \neq ((A_t \vee \neg B_t) \wedge (\neg A_t \vee B_t)) \quad (194)$$

□

3.9. Necessary and sufficient condition

Theorem 14 (Necessary and sufficient condition). *In general, it is*

$$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) = ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t) = ((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) \quad (195)$$

Proof. We want to prove that,

$$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) = ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t) = ((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) \quad (196)$$

Let us break down this equality into various parts, as demonstrated (Table 23).

Table 23. Necessary and sufficient condition between (U_t) and (W_t)

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t))$	$((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)$	$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t))$
1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	0	1	0	0
3	0	1	0	1	0
4	0	0	1	1	1
...	...	...	...	...	...

Therefore, we have shown that

$$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) = ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t) = ((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)) \quad (197)$$

□

The preceding proof holds considerable practical significance. It is highly valuable that one and the same study can provide evidence for a necessary condition, a sufficient condition, a necessary and sufficient condition, and ultimately, for the causal relationship. However, for various reasons such as study design, sensitivity and specificity of employed methods, the primer used, diligence, and technical proficiency of the investigator, among others, this will more likely be the exception than the rule in scientific research. However, we may draw upon various studies for our causal argumentation based on the preceding theorem (Theorem 14). If Study A has demonstrated the proof of a necessary condition, and, for example, Study B has demonstrated the proof of a sufficient condition, these results can indeed be considered in accordance with the previous theorem (Theorem 14) in establishing a causal connection in the argumentation. Nevertheless, a certain natural restraint is advisable in this regard, especially in the event that the various studies originate from significantly different temporal periods.

3.10. Necessary and sufficient condition ($p(a_t) + p(d_t) = 1$) and causation ($k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$)

A causal relationship refers to the cause-and-effect relation between (two) variables. Thus far, as an example, in a causal relationship, excessive rain (cause) may be a factor leading to flooding (effect). In

contrast to a causal relationship, a necessary and sufficient conditions focus on logical and conceptual connections. As an example, bakers often use yeast in the bread production process. It is known that **without** the use of yeast, **no** rise occurs in the bread. Therefore, yeast is a necessary condition for bread to rise. Furthermore, **if** yeast is used, **then** the bread is rising. Thus, yeast is also a sufficient condition for bread to rise. In essence, the proper use of yeast is both a necessary and sufficient condition for the bread to rise. What, then, is the identity and difference (Brand and Swain, 1970, 1974; De Morgan, 1847; Gomes, Gilberto, 2009; Hilpinen, 1974; Sanford, 1978) between a (necessary and sufficient) condition and causation? The following theorem describes the difficulties in providing complete precision in answering this question.

3.11. The identity of necessary and sufficient condition and causation

Theorem 15 (Identity of necessary and sufficient condition and causation). *There are circumstances, where a necessary and sufficient condition is identical to causation. Under certain circumstances, it is*

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = k(U_t, W_t) = 1 \quad (198)$$

Proof by thought experiment. We conduct an ideal thought experiment and obtain data as follows (Table 24).

Table 24. Necessary and sufficient condition between (U_t) and (W_t) and causation

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$(U_t \vee (\neg W_t))$	$((\neg U_t) \vee W_t)$	$((U_t \vee (\neg W_t)) \wedge ((\neg U_t) \vee W_t))$	$k(U_t, W_t)$
1	1	1	1	1	1	1
2	1	1	1	1	1	1
3	0	0	1	1	1	1
4	0	0	1	1	1	1
...	...	...	...	...	...	...

As can be seen, there are circumstances where the necessary and sufficient condition and causality are identical.

□

3.12. The difference between a necessary and sufficient condition and causation

Theorem 16 (The difference between a necessary and sufficient condition and causation). *There are circumstances, where a necessary and sufficient condition is different from causation. In general, it is*

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) \neq k(U_t, W_t) \quad (199)$$

Proof by contradiction. We begin by assuming the opposite (negation) of Equation 199 we want to prove. Therefore, we suppose that this assumption

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (200)$$

is true and generally valid. As next, we derive consequences or implications from the assumed statement as follows. We conduct another thought experiment under ideal conditions and obtain the following data: $p(a_t) = 0.25$, $p(b_t) = 0.25$, $p(U_t) = p(a_t) + p(b_t) = 0.5$, $p(c_t) = 0.25$, $p(d_t) = 0.25$, $p(W_t) = p(a_t) + p(c_t) = 0.5$. Under these conditions, we obtain

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) = 0.25 + 0.25 = \frac{(p(\text{R}U_t, \text{R}W_t) - (p(\text{R}U_t) \times p(\text{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p(\text{R}U_t) \times (1 - p(\text{R}U_t)) \times p(\text{R}W_t) \times (1 - p(\text{R}W_t))}} = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (201)$$

or

$$0.5 = \frac{(p(\text{R}U_t, \text{R}W_t) - (p(\text{R}U_t) \times p(\text{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p(\text{R}U_t) \times (1 - p(\text{R}U_t)) \times p(\text{R}W_t) \times (1 - p(\text{R}W_t))}} = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (202)$$

or

$$0.5 = \frac{((0.25) - ((0.5) \times (0.5)))}{\sqrt[2]{(0.5) \times (1 - (0.5)) \times (0.5) \times (1 - (0.5))}} = k(U_t, W_t) \quad (203)$$

or

$$0.5 = 0 \quad (204)$$

As next, we divide Equation 204 by 0.5 and do obtain

$$1 = 0 \quad (205)$$

The negation of the original statement leads to an untenable situation. The opposite of what we wanted to prove leads to a logical contradiction. However, if the opposite of what we wanted to prove leads to an impossible logical situation, then what we wanted to prove must be correct. Therefore, since our assumption leads to a contradiction, the original statement must be true. In general, it is

$$p(a_t) + p(d_t) \neq k(U_t, W_t) \quad (206)$$

□

This theorem can have practical implications for everyday research. It is beneficial if studies can provide evidence for a necessary and sufficient condition. This has the potential to increase the level of evidence supporting a possible causal relationship between events under investigation. However, such an approach is not a substitute for demonstrating a causal relationship per se.

3.13. Causation and coincidence of events

Phenomena may appear at first glance interconnected due to their simultaneous manifestation but yet lack inherent causal significance. Coincidence as the co-occurrence of events or processes simultaneously (according to Einstein's special (Einstein, 1905) theory of relativity) does not necessarily

imply a causal relationship between them. Therefore, understanding coincidence as such necessitates a very careful consideration of causality, as events occurring together do not necessarily possess a direct cause-and-effect relationship. A theory of causality, which is based solely on the co-occurrence of events, would commit the so-called cum hoc ergo propter hoc logical fallacy. Cum hoc ergo propter hoc is a logical fallacy that occurs when scholars assume that because two events happen simultaneously, the one must be the cause of the other. In English, the cum hoc ergo propter hoc logical fallacy translates to “with this, therefore because of this”. This fallacy muddles the fundamentals of causation by suggesting that the mere simultaneous occurrence of two events implies a causal relationship between them. It is crucial to acknowledge that the co-occurrence of events does not necessarily establish causation, and such simultaneity might be coincidental rather than indicative of a cause-and-effect relationship.

Theorem 17 (Causation and coincidence of events). *The basic relationship between a cause (U_t) and an effect (W_t) is given logically (Table 25) as follows:*

Table 25. The relationship between cause (U_t) and effect (W_t)

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0
3	0	1	0
4	0	0	0
...	...	...	...

Proof by Induction. We will prove the relationship above by induction on the variable t .

Base Case (Bernoulli trial $t = 1$): Cause and Effect

Assume U_1 is true and W_1 is true. Then, the coincidence of cause and effect is given by the conjunction ($\wedge$) operation as:

$$U_1 \wedge W_1 = 1 \wedge 1 = 1 \quad (207)$$

or more generally as

Table 26. Cause and Effect

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
1	1	1	1
...	...	...	...

Leibniz posited the equivalence of cause and effect (“**aequationem ... causam et effectum**” (Leibniz, 1690, p. 201)). Hegel further refined this concept by eloquently expounding on the identity of a

cause with its own effect.

“Cause is cause only in so far as it produces an effect, and cause is nothing but this determination, to have an effect, and effect is nothing but this, to have a cause. Cause as such implies its effect, and effect implies cause; in so far as cause has not yet acted, or if it has ceased to act, then it is not cause, and effect in so far as its cause has vanished, is no longer effect but an indifferent actuality.” (Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 559)

Coincidence of events refers to the co-occurrence of events simultaneously or more generally at the same Bernoulli trial t or at the same (period of) time t or at the same run of an experiment t . Yet, the coincidence or co-occurrence of events doesn't inherently and under any circumstances imply causation, the coincidence of events alone is insufficient to definitively prove causation. The alignment of an event (the cause) with another event (the effect) inherently forms a crucial foundation of causal connection, as illustrated in Bernoulli trial 1. However, the mere coincidence of events alone is not adequate to establish causation conclusively. Coincidence alone lacks the necessary evidence to prove causation, as additional aspect of the relationship between cause and effect need to be considered in order to establish a more rigorous concept of causality that aligns with objective reality in full concordance. However, the coincidence of a cause as whole with its own other, with its own effect as the absence of separation of what is separable carries within itself its own opposite. In other words, a theory of causality relying solely on coincidence of events commits the so-called “cum hoc ergo propter hoc”logical fallacy. Events occurring simultaneously may be causally linked, but the co-occurrence of events does not guarantee causation. The “cum hoc ergo propter hoc”logical fallacy is a flawed conclusion that arises when causation between two events is assumed simply because they occur simultaneously. This assumption overlooks other possible explanations for the relationship between the events, and erroneously assumes that such a co-occurrence of events necessarily implies a cause-and-effect relationship. The error lies in the fact that coincidence alone is insufficient to confirm a causal connection, as other factors or causes could influence the relationship. The term is derived from Latin and means ‘With this, therefore because of this,’ accurately describing the misleading inference. Especially, the scenarios where a cause has no effect or an effect has no cause need to be considered separately and in more detail.

Base Case (*Bernoulli trial* $t = 2$): if Cause, then Effect

Assume U_1 is true and W_1 is false. Then,

$$U_1 \wedge W_1 = 1 \wedge 0 = 0 \quad (208)$$

or

Table 27. Cause with no Effect

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
...	...	...	...
2	1	0	0
...	...	...	...

Bernoulli trial $t = 2$ implies a cause ($U_t = 1$) without its own effect ($W_t = 0$), a cause need not produce an effect. The relationship, if cause, then effect (Table 27) is illustrated by the next table (Table 28) from a different point of view. A cause is a sufficient condition of an effect.

Table 28. If cause, then effect

		Effect W_t		
		YES = 1	NO = 0	
Cause	YES = 1	1	($b_t = 0$)	U_t
U_t	NO = 0	0	1	$\underline{U}_t$
		W_t	$\underline{W}_t$	1

Hegel concisely captures the fundamental nature of the cause-and-effect relationship once more. In his concise expression, Hegel reaffirms the foundational understanding of the cause-effect dynamic.

“Cause as such implies its effect ... ” (Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 559)

In the event that a cause need not produce an effect, it equally raises fundamental questions about the necessity of any causality. Such a solitary observation, exemplified by Bernoulli trial $t = 2$, where a cause is present, but the effect does not manifest, carries substantial significance as a potential counterexample to causation. This unique and isolated incident challenges conventional notions of causation, prompting inquiries into the presumed deterministic connection between cause and effect. In other words, a cause must have an effect, a cause without an effect is something else, but not a cause. For this reason, we obtain $U_t \wedge W_t = 0$. In such a scenario, we don't consider it a valid case of causation.

Base Case (Bernoulli trial $t = 3$): Without a Cause, no Effect

Assume U_1 is false and W_1 is true. Then,

$$U_1 \wedge W_1 = 0 \wedge 1 = 0 \quad (209)$$

or

Table 29. Without a Cause, no Effect

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
...	...	...	...
3	0	1	0
...	...	...	...

Bernoulli trial $t = 3$ implies no cause ($U_t = 0$) and effect ($W_t = 1$), an effect can occur without its own cause (Table 29). In general, a cause is a necessary condition of an effect, without a cause, no effect (Table 30).

Table 30. Without a cause, no effect

		Effect W_t		
		YES = 1	NO = 0	
Cause	YES = 1	1	0	U_t
U_t	NO = 0	($c_t = 0$)	1	U_t
		W_t	W_t	1

In the event that an effect can occur without its cause, it raises fundamental questions about the necessity of causation. The consequence of such a possibility may suggest a reevaluation of the concept of causality altogether. This poses a challenge to the traditional understanding of cause and effect, potentially prompting a reconsideration of our assumptions about the fundamental nature of causal relationships. Still, let us suppose an effect could occur without a cause. What significance would even a single occurrence of such an event hold for the relationship between cause and effect? In our comprehension of the deterministic connection between a cause and an effect, the existence of an effect without a cause is not possible. In simpler terms, if we observe an effect, there must be at least one cause responsible for it. For this reason, we obtain $U_t \wedge W_t = 0$. In such a scenario, we don't consider $U_t \wedge W_t = 0$ a valid case of causation. Hegel described the cause as the necessary condition for the effect in the following manner.

“... an ... effect in so far as its cause has vanished, is no longer effect but an indifferent actuality.” (Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 559)

Base Case (Bernoulli trial $t = 4$): No Cause and no Effect

Assume U_1 is false and W_1 is false. Then,

$$U_1 \wedge W_1 = 0 \wedge 0 = 0 \quad (210)$$

or

Table 31. No Cause and No Effect

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
...	...	...	...
4	0	0	0
...	...	...	...

Bernoulli trial $t = 4$ demonstrate circumstances where neither a cause nor an effect is present, indicating a lack of causation. What, if anything at all, can be said about the deterministic relationship between cause and effect under these circumstances? Often, causality is simplistically understood as “If the cause U has occurred, then the effect W has also occurred”. However, causality can also be defined ex negativo, meaning “If cause U has not occurred, then effect W does not occur”. This situation is precisely described by Bernoulli trial $t = 4$. Yet, counterfactual theories of causation (Lewis, David Kellogg, 1973, 1974), particularly the basic idea that explains causal claims in terms of counterfactual conditionals like “If cause U had not occurred, the effect W would not have occurred too”, offer an approach to causation ex negativo. However, this one-sided approach to causality is of limited value for various reasons.

Example. Let us assume that smoking is the cause of lung cancer in person A. If person A had not smoked (no cause), the effect (lung cancer) would not have occurred. However, even if person A had her lungs removed and continued to live with the aid of a suitable lung machine, the lung cancer (effect) would not have occurred. This implies that the non-existence of person A’s lungs would be a cause of her lung cancer. However, how can person A develop lung cancer when she has no lungs? The counterfactual theory of causation leads to numerous contradictions and is overly one-sided.

Inductive Step:

Assume the proposition holds for $t = k$, i.e., $U_k \wedge W_k = U_k \times W_k$.

Now, we want to show it holds for $t = k + 1$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 U_{k+1} \wedge W_{k+1} &= U_{k+1} \times W_{k+1} \\
 (U_k \wedge W_k) \wedge (U_{k+1} \wedge W_{k+1}) &= (U_k \times W_k) \times (U_{k+1} \times W_{k+1}) \\
 U_k \wedge W_k \wedge U_{k+1} \wedge W_{k+1} &= U_k \times W_k \times U_{k+1} \times W_{k+1}
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the inductive step. Through this proof by induction, we can establish that the conjunction of cause and effect is foundational to the causal relationship as

Table 32. Cause (U_t) and effect (W_t)

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$
1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0
3	0	1	0
4	0	0	0
...	...	...	...

By mathematical induction, the proposition holds for all t .

□

As generally known, Hegel's theory of causality centers on the dialectical interplay between a cause and an effect.

“Thus, in the causal relation, cause and effect are inseparable; a cause which had no effect would not be a cause, just as an effect which had no cause would no longer be an effect. ” (Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 151)

Hegel emphasizes the dynamic nature of causality, viewing causality as an integral part of the evolving of reality. In his philosophical framework, Hegel demands that causation is not merely a linear sequence but a complex, interconnected process which is determined by the inherent unity of opposites. The relationship between a cause and an effect as an inherent unity of opposites and their dialectical interaction is illuminated by the following profound philosophical statement of Hegel. “... something is determined as cause, but ... it, too, has a cause, that is, it is also an effect; hence the same thing that was determined as cause is also determined as effect - the unity of cause and effect; now that which is determined as effect again has a cause, that is, the cause has to be separated from its effect ... as a different something; but this ... cause is itself only an effect - the unity of cause and effect; it has another for its cause - the separation of both determinations, and so on ... ” (Hegel, Georg Wilhelm Friedrich, 1991, p. 151)

3.14. The causal relationship k

Theorem 18 (Causal relationship k). *Thus far, let $p({}_R U_t)$ represent the probability from the point of view of a stationary observer R of a certain cause ${}_R U_t$, i. e. a random variable or a quantum mechanical observable or a cluster inside a set, at a certain Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R U_t^2)$ denote the expectation value of the cause ${}_R U_t^2$. Let $E({}_R U_t)$ denote the expectation value of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)$ denote the standard deviation of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t)^2$ denote the variance of the cause ${}_R U_t$. Let $p({}_R W_t)$ represent the probability from the point of view of a stationary observer R of its own*

effect ${}_R W_t$, i. e. a random variable or a quantum mechanical observable or a cluster inside a set, at a certain Bernoulli trial t . Let $E({}_R W_t^2)$ denote the expectation value of the effect ${}_R W_t^2$. Let $E({}_R W_t)$ denote the expectation value of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R W_t)$ denote the standard deviation of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R W_t)^2$ denote the variance of the effect ${}_R W_t$. Let $\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$ denote the co-variance of cause ${}_R U_t$ and effect ${}_R W_t$. The causal relationship, denoted as $k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$, inside a sets can be calculated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sqrt{\sigma({}_R U_t)^2 \times \sigma({}_R W_t)^2}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \\
 &\equiv \frac{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt{(({}_R U_t^2) \times (p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times ({}_R W_t^2) \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))))}} \quad (211) \\
 &\equiv \frac{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times (p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \times \sqrt{((p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))))}} \\
 &\equiv \frac{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt{((p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))) \times (p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))))}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof by modus ponens. **If** the premise

$$\underbrace{+1 = +1}_{(Premise)} \quad (212)$$

is true, **then** the conclusion

$$k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \quad (213)$$

is also true, the absence of any technical errors presupposed. The premise

$$+1 \equiv +1 \quad (214)$$

is true. Multiplying this premise (i. e. axiom) by the a single cause $({}_R U_t)$ at a certain Bernoulli trial t , it is

$$({}_R U_t) \equiv ({}_R U_t) \quad (215)$$

Multiplying the cause (equation 215) by its own effect $({}_R W_t)$ it is

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv ({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \quad (216)$$

The basis of Equation 216 is Theorem 11, Equation 178.

Table 33. Conjunction ($\wedge$) and Multiplication ($\times$)

Bernoulli trial t	U_t	W_t	$U_t \wedge W_t$	$U_t \times W_t$
1	1	1	1	1
2	1	0	0	0
3	0	1	0	0
4	0	0	0	0
...	...	...	...	...

Accordingly, the identity of conjugation and multiplication (Table 33) is a mathematical approach in order to describe the relationship between a cause and an effect in a logically consistent manner (Theorem 17). Thus far, based on Equation 82 it is

$${}_R U_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \quad (217)$$

with the consequence that equation 216 changes to

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \times {}_R W_t \quad (218)$$

According to equation 83 it is

$${}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \quad (219)$$

and equation 218 changes to

$$({}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t) \equiv \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \times \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \right) \quad (220)$$

According to definition 2.25, equation 86, it is

$${}_R U_t \times {}_R W_t \equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))} \quad (221)$$

Simplifying equation 220 it is

$$\left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))} \right) \equiv \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R U_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))}} \right) \times \left(\frac{\sigma({}_R W_t)}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \right) \quad (222)$$

Further rearrangement of equation 222 yields the causal relationship between a cause ${}_R U_t$ and an effect ${}_R W_t$, denoted as $k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)$, as

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) &\equiv \frac{\sigma({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t)}{\sigma({}_R U_t) \times \sigma({}_R W_t)} \\ &\equiv \frac{(p({}_R U_t, {}_R W_t) - (p({}_R U_t) \times p({}_R W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_R U_t) \times (1 - p({}_R U_t))} \times \sqrt[2]{p({}_R W_t) \times (1 - p({}_R W_t))}} \end{aligned} \quad (223)$$

3.15. The causal relationship k and the binomial distribution

Theorem 19 (Causal relationship k and binomial distribution). *Under the conditions of binomially distributed random variables, the causal relationship k undergoes a transformation into*

$$k({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) = \frac{(N \times E(a)) - (E(U) \times E(W))}{\sqrt[2]{E(U) \times E(U) \times E(W) \times E(W)}} \quad (224)$$

Direct proof. Under conditions of a binomial distribution, the probability from trial to trial is constant. The causal relationship becomes

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) &\equiv \frac{(p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \\ &\equiv \frac{N \times N \times ((p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t))))}{N \times N \times \sqrt[2]{p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \end{aligned} \quad (225)$$

where N is the population (i.e. sample) size. Equation 225 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) &\equiv \frac{(p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \\ &\equiv \frac{(N \times N \times (p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (N \times N \times p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t))))}{\sqrt[2]{N \times N \times p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times N \times N \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \end{aligned} \quad (226)$$

Equation 226 becomes

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) &\equiv \frac{(p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \\ &\equiv \frac{(N \times N \times (p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (N \times p({}_{R}U_t) \times N \times p({}_{R}W_t))))}{\sqrt[2]{N \times p({}_{R}U_t) \times N \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times N \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times N \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \end{aligned} \quad (227)$$

Under the conditions of binomially distributed random variables, the causal relationship k undergoes a transformation. Equation 227 (Table 3) changes to

$$\begin{aligned} k({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) &\equiv \frac{(p({}_{R}U_t, {}_{R}W_t) - (p({}_{R}U_t) \times p({}_{R}W_t)))}{\sqrt[2]{p({}_{R}U_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}U_t)) \times p({}_{R}W_t) \times (1 - p({}_{R}W_t))}} \\ &\equiv \frac{(N \times E(a)) - (E(U) \times E(W))}{\sqrt[2]{E(U) \times E(U) \times E(W) \times E(W)}} \end{aligned} \quad (228)$$

These relationships will be visualized as follows (Table 34) for better understanding.

Table 34. Causal relationship and binomial distribution.

		Effect W		E(U)
		YES = TRUE	NO = FALSE	
Cause	YES = TRUE	E(a)		E(U)
	U	NO = FALSE	E(U)	
		E(W)	E(W)	N

The theory of correlation in mathematics has a very long history. As long as we can rely on the preliminary investigations in this matter by Pearson himself, authors such as Bravais, Dickson, Galton, Edgeworth, and others have made fundamental contributions. Pearson writes:

“The fundamental theorems of correlation were for the first time and almost exhaustively discussed by Bravais (*Analyse mathématique sur le probabilités des erreurs de situation d’un point.* Mémoires par divers Savans, T. IX., Paris, 1846, pp. 255-332) nearly half a century ago. He deals completely with the correlation of two and three variables. ” (Pearson, 1896, p. 261)

Over time, a modern form of the correlation coefficient developed through various adaptations to diverse theoretical conditions, taking the shape of the Bravais-Pearson’s correlation coefficient. However, the Bravais-Pearson’s correlation coefficient is nothing more than an epistemological and evolutionary precursor to the causal relationship k . The relationship between the Bravais-Pearson correlation coefficient and the causal relationship k can be likened to the connection between a great ape and *Homo sapiens*. Both share common ancestors and bear a strong resemblance, yet they are not identical. Under no conceivable circumstances does it make sense to reduce the intricate nature of the causal relationship k to the simplicity of Bravais [Bravais \(1846\)](#) (1811-1863) - **Pearson’s coefficient of correlation** [Galton \(1877\)](#); [Pearson \(1896\)](#), or to **Pearson’s phi coefficient** [Pearson \(1904\)](#).

Karl Pearson introduced the phi coefficient in his paper titled ‘On the Theory of Contingency and Its Relation to Association and Normal Correlation,’ published in the journal ‘*Biometrika*’ in 1900 (Volume 2, Issue 4, pages 105-124) [Pearson \(1904\)](#). In contrast to the causal relationship k , the limitations of the Bravais-Pearson’s correlation coefficient and the Pearson-Phi coefficient become apparent. These traditional correlation measures fall short in capturing the complexity of various causal scenarios, such as those found in causal chains or in causal scenarios where one cause is leading to multiple effects, multiple causes are resulting in a single effect, or a multitude of causes is leading to various effects ([Barukčić, 1989, 2006, 2020a, 2021](#); [Barukčić, 1997, 2005, 2016b,c, 2017b,c](#)). Contrastingly, the causal relationship k proves versatile and universally applicable, even under conditions of Einstein’s general theory of relativity ([Barukčić, 2016c](#)). The causal relationship k surpasses the limitations associated with particular distributions, proving versatile in its application to the examination of continuous random variables and cumulative distribution functions as well. This adaptability allows the causal relationship k to reveal nuanced cause-and-effect relationships, making it a powerful tool for discerning

intricate patterns of influence. In summary, while the Bravais-Pearson correlation coefficient and the Pearson-Phi coefficient have their utility in measuring linear associations, they lack the robustness needed to explore the diverse and intricate causal relationships encapsulated by k . The latter emerges as a more comprehensive and flexible metric for capturing the multifaceted nature of cause-and-effect dynamics across various scenarios of objective reality.

Karl Pearson (1857-1936), a prominent statistician and biometrician, had a distinctive theory of causality that differed from traditional philosophical notions. Pearson's perspective on causation was largely influenced by his work in statistics and the empirical sciences. At the end, Pearson unequivocally "rejected causal thinking" (Blalock, 1972, p. 39) and embraced a perspective that leaned towards correlation over causation.

“It is this conception of correlation ... by which we have to replace ... causation.
” (Pearson, 1911, p. 157)

In his approach to causation, Pearson emphasized the role of the observer or individual in perceiving and interpreting causal relationships, his concept of causation is rooted in the regularity of sequences observed by a subject and is highly subjective. In the extreme, Pearson denies any causation by claiming that

“... there is association but not causation. ” (Pearson, 1911, p. 169)

Theorem 20 (Phi Coefficient and Causation). *The Pearson Phi coefficient, denoted by ϕ , quantifies the strength and direction of association between two binary variables. However, Pearson Phi coefficient is not identical with the causal relationship k . In contrast to Pearson Phi coefficient, which is calculated based on observed frequencies in a contingency table, the causal relationship k is valid for any distribution, including continuous random variables too without any restriction.*

Pearson underscores that causation from his point of view emerges from the temporal succession of events, and the link between the subject and causation is established through the way an individual perceives events in a specific temporal order.

“We are now in a position to define cause as used in science. Whenever a sequence of perception D, E, F, G is invariably preceded by the perception C, or the perceptions C, D, E, F, G always occur in this order, that is, form a routine of experience, C is said to be a cause of D, E, F, G, which are then described as its effects. ” (Pearson, 1911, p. 130)

A cause, according to Pearson, is an event that was invariably followed by a specific sequence of perceptions and not something existing independently and outside human mind and consciousness. These perceptions are pivotal in shaping an individual's understanding of cause and effect, as patterns and consistencies in the sequence of experiences become apparent. Pearson contends that the concept of causation is intricately tied to subjective experiences and the continuous flow of individual perceptions, relying entirely on the human mind and consciousness.

“... we saw the foundation of the idea of causation in the routine of perceptions.” (Pearson, 1911, p. 152)

According to Pearson, causation, in his view, is not an objective and real phenomenon but a concept reliant on the subjective interpretation of temporal associations in sequences of perceptions. At the end,

“... Association, as replacing Causation.” (Pearson, 1911, p. 156)

is enough. Pearson’s philosophical stance on causation is highly subjective, highlighting its dependence on the human mind and consciousness. Pearson goes so far as to assert that causation lacks any scientific significance, unequivocally stating that “... correlation ... have to replace ... causation” (Pearson, 1911, p. 157). Pearson vehemently denies any necessity for an independent concept of causal relation beyond correlation. Furthermore, Pearson’s theory of causality was characterized by an extreme subjectivity tied to the observer’s perception, the emphasis on temporal patterns in sequences of events and its statistical nature. In the last consequence, Pearson “... exterminated causation from statistics before it had a chance to take root” (Pearl, 2000, p. 340). Emphasizing the regularity of sequences in experience, Pearson posits it as the fundamental basis for recognizing causes and effects, asserting the temporal succession of events as an indispensable cornerstone of causality. Pearson’s understanding of causation is derived straightforward from Hume’s post hoc, ergo propter hoc logical fallacy based regularity theory of causation.

3.15.1. Correlation $\neq$ Causation

The correlation coefficient represents an epistemological mechanistic view of the relationship between two quantitative variables.

Theorem 21 (Correlation $\neq$ Causation). *Let X denote a quantity. Let $E(X)$ denote the expectation value of this quantity. Let Y denote another quantity. Let $E(Y)$ denote the expectation value of this quantity. The correlation coefficient is a measure of linearity between these two quantities X and Y , but not of causation. It is*

$$\rho = \frac{\text{Cov}(X \times Y)}{\sigma(X) \times \sigma(Y)} \quad (229)$$

Proof. The foundation of this proof is based on the assumption that the quantities X and Y , even if different, are identical too. In general, it is,

$$X = Y \quad (230)$$

$$X^2 = Y^2 \quad (231)$$

$$E(X) = E(Y) \quad (232)$$

$$E(X^2) = E(Y^2) \quad (233)$$

Based on Equation 230 and Equation 232, we (Kolmogoroff, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1933, p. 38) obtain (Kolmogorov, Andreï Nikolaevich, 1950, p. 42):

$$E(X^2) - E(X)^2 = E(X - E(X))E(X - E(X)) = E(X - E(X)) \times E(Y - E(Y)) \quad (234)$$

$$E(X \times X) - (E(X) \times E(X)) = \sigma(X) \times E(Y - E(Y)) \quad (235)$$

$$E(X \times Y) - (E(X) \times E(Y)) = \sigma(X) \times \sigma(Y) \quad (236)$$

$$\text{Cov}(X \times Y) = \sigma(X) \times \sigma(Y) \quad (237)$$

At the end it is

$$\rho = \frac{\text{Cov}(X \times Y)}{\sigma(X) \times \sigma(Y)} \quad (238)$$

□

Theorem 22 (Correlation ≠ Causation). *The correlation coefficient measures the strength and direction of a linear relationship between two quantities. However, correlation does not imply causation. In general, it is*

$$\text{Correlation} \neq \text{Causation} \quad (239)$$

Proof by counter-example. Let X denote the cost of bread in Britain. Let Y denote the sea level in Venice (Italy). Both quantities, the sea level in Venice and the cost of bread in Britain, have been increased steadily with time. In other words, higher than average sea levels tend to be associated with higher than average bread prices, both quantities are strongly positively correlated (Sober, 2001). The question arises, how does the cost of bread in Britain causes the sea level in Venice to increase. This counter-example demonstrates that a high correlation between two variables does not imply a causal relationship. □

3.16. Methods and objective reality

Next, we will integrate advanced statistical techniques with available health data to offer valuable insights into a critically important scientific concern: the relationship between Parvovirus B19, a single stranded DNA virus which has wide varieties of clinical manifestations and acute myeloid leukaemia.

3.16.1. Without Parvovirus B19 infection, no acute myeloid leukaemia

Table 35. Relationship: Without Parvovirus B19, no AML.

		AML		
		YES	NO	
Parvovirus B19	YES	31	2	33
	NO	1	58	59
		32	60	92

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,92890808$
P Value (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000000
p (SINE) = 0,98913043
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/B) > 0,96875000
p (SINE) approx.= 1-(c/(Not A)) > 0,98305085

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— Not A_i) = 0,02
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE— B_i) = 0,03
P Value (SINE) = **0,01081070**

PROPORTIONS.

(a/N) × 100 = (31 / 92) × 100 = 33,70 %
(b/N) × 100 = (2 / 92) × 100 = 2,17 %
(c/N) × 100 = (1 / 92) × 100 = 1,09 %
(d/N) × 100 = (58 / 92) × 100 = 63,04 %
(a/A) × 100 = (31 / 33) × 100 = 93,94 %
(b/A) × 100 = (2 / 33) × 100 = 6,06 %
(c/ not A) × 100 = (1 / 59) × 100 = 1,69 %
(d/ not A) × 100 = (58 / 59) × 100 = 98,31 %
(a/B) × 100 = (31 / 32) × 100 = 96,88 %
(c/B) × 100 = (1 / 32) × 100 = 3,13 %
(b/ not B) × 100 = (2 / 60) × 100 = 3,33 %
(d/ not B) × 100 = (58 / 60) × 100 = 96,67 %
(A/N) × 100 = (33 / 92) × 100 = 35,87 %
(not A/N) × 100 = (59 / 92) × 100 = 64,13 %
(B/N) × 100 = (32 / 92) × 100 = 34,78 %
(not B/N) × 100 = (60 / 92) × 100 = 65,22 %

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 55,42424242
RR (sufficient condition) = 29,06250000

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 899,00000000
Index of relationship (IOR) = 1,70075758

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU)= **0,29347826**
p(IOI)= 0,01086957

3.16.1.1. Fisher's exact test Sir Ronald Aylmer Fisher (1890-1962) is credited as the first to define and publish Fisher's exact test (Fisher, 1935b). This pivotal statistical method is a statistical signifi-

cance test, which enable us to calculate the significance of the deviation from a null hypothesis (e.g., P Value) exactly. It is a widely adopted practice to utilize Fisher’s exact test, especially when dealing with small sample sizes. However, it is important to note that Fisher’s exact test is valid and applicable across a broad range of sample sizes.

3.16.1.1.1. One sided right-tailed Fisher’s exact test Fisher’s exact one sided right-tailed test is calculated as follows.

$$\begin{aligned}
 p(X \geq a) &= 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{a-1} \frac{\binom{A}{i} \binom{N-A}{B-i}}{\binom{N}{B}} \\
 &= 1 - \sum_{i=0}^{31-1} \frac{\binom{33}{i} \binom{92-33}{32-i}}{\binom{92}{32}} \tag{240} \\
 &= 0,0000000000 \\
 &= \text{P Value (one sided right tailed)}
 \end{aligned}$$

3.16.2. If Parvovirus B19 infection, then acute myeloid leukaemia

A sufficient condition is an event, a circumstance or statement et cetera that, if true, guarantees the occurrence of a particular outcome or event. In other words, the presence of such an event, a circumstance et cetera alone is enough to ensure another specified outcome, event or result. In general, if the sufficient condition is met, the event is certain to happen. The data published by El-Khier (Tharwat Abou El-Khier et al., 2018) et al. have been reanalysed (Table 36).

Table 36. If Parvovirus B19, then AML.

		AML		
		YES	NO	
Parvovirus B19	YES	31	2	33
	NO	1	58	59
		32	60	92

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = +0,92890808$
 P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000000
 p (IMP) = 0,97826087
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/A) > 0,93939394$
 p (IMP) approx.= $1-(b/(Not B)) > 0,96666667$

P VALUES.

$\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— A_i) = 0,12
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (IMP— Not B_i) = 0,07
 P Value (IMP) = 0,02150454

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (31 / 92) \times 100 = 33,70 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2 / 92) \times 100 = 2,17 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1 / 92) \times 100 = 1,09 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (58 / 92) \times 100 = 63,04 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (31 / 33) \times 100 = 93,94 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2 / 33) \times 100 = 6,06 \%$
 $(c/ not A) \times 100 = (1 / 59) \times 100 = 1,69 \%$
 $(d/ not A) \times 100 = (58 / 59) \times 100 = 98,31 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (31 / 32) \times 100 = 96,88 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1 / 32) \times 100 = 3,13 \%$
 $(b/ not B) \times 100 = (2 / 60) \times 100 = 3,33 \%$
 $(d/ not B) \times 100 = (58 / 60) \times 100 = 96,67 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (33 / 92) \times 100 = 35,87 \%$
 $(not A/N) \times 100 = (59 / 92) \times 100 = 64,13 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (32 / 92) \times 100 = 34,78 \%$
 $(not B/N) \times 100 = (60 / 92) \times 100 = 65,22 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 55,42424242
 RR (sufficient condition) = 29,06250000

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 899,00000000
 Index of relationship (IOR) = 1,70075758

STUDY DESIGN.

p (IOU)= 0,29347826
 p (IOI)= 0,01086957

We must note that a corresponding infection with PVB19 is a sufficient condition for AML (P Value

= 0). In other words, if a certain kind of PVB19 infection, then AML.

3.16.3. Parvovirus B19 infection is a necessary and sufficient condition of acute myeloid leukaemia

The data published by El-Khier et al. (Tharwat Abou El-Khier et al., 2018) have been reanalysed (Table 37) to examine whether a necessary and sufficient condition exists between PVB19 and AML.

Table 37. Necessary and sufficient condition: PVB19 and AML.

		AML		
		YES	NO	
Parvovirus B19	YES	31	2	33
	NO	1	58	59
		32	60	92

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS.

Causal relationship $k = 0,92890808$
P Value (one sided right tailed) (Fisher's exact test) = 0,00000000
p (SINE and IMP) = 0,98913043

P VALUES.

P Value (one sided right tailed) (HGD) = 0,00000000
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE and IMP— A_t) = 0,14
 $\tilde{\chi}^2$ (SINE and IMP— B_t) = 0,10
P Value (SINE and IMP) = **0,03208276**

PROPORTIONS.

$(a/N) \times 100 = (31 / 92) \times 100 = 33,70 \%$
 $(b/N) \times 100 = (2 / 92) \times 100 = 2,17 \%$
 $(c/N) \times 100 = (1 / 92) \times 100 = 1,09 \%$
 $(d/N) \times 100 = (58 / 92) \times 100 = 63,04 \%$
 $(a/A) \times 100 = (31 / 33) \times 100 = 93,94 \%$
 $(b/A) \times 100 = (2 / 33) \times 100 = 6,06 \%$
 $(c/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (1 / 59) \times 100 = 1,69 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } A) \times 100 = (58 / 59) \times 100 = 98,31 \%$
 $(a/B) \times 100 = (31 / 32) \times 100 = 96,88 \%$
 $(c/B) \times 100 = (1 / 32) \times 100 = 3,13 \%$
 $(b/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (2 / 60) \times 100 = 3,33 \%$
 $(d/\text{not } B) \times 100 = (58 / 60) \times 100 = 96,67 \%$
 $(A/N) \times 100 = (33 / 92) \times 100 = 35,87 \%$
 $(\text{not } A/N) \times 100 = (59 / 92) \times 100 = 64,13 \%$
 $(B/N) \times 100 = (32 / 92) \times 100 = 34,78 \%$
 $(\text{not } B/N) \times 100 = (60 / 92) \times 100 = 65,22 \%$

ADDITIONAL STATISTICAL MEASURES.

RELATIVE RISK (RR).

RR (necessary condition) = 55,42424242
RR (sufficient condition) = 29,06250000

OTHER STATISTICAL MEASURES.

Odds ratio (OR) = 899,00000000
Index of relationship (IOR) = 1,70075758

STUDY DESIGN.

p(IOU) = 0,29347826
p(IOD) = **0,01086957**

Based on the data provided to the public by El-Khier et al. (Tharwat Abou El-Khier et al., 2018), we must assume that there is a relationship of a necessary and sufficient condition between PVB19 and AML (P Value = 0).

4. Discussion

Tunc Fisgin et al. (Fisgin et al., 2002) reported in the year 2002 an unusual presentation of acute myeloblastic leukemia (AML) preceded by acute Parvovirus B19 infection. Soon, Us (Us et al., 2007) et al. found in the year 2007 Parvovirus 19 in patients with AML. In this publication, we were able to subject the data published by El-Khier et al. to a closer examination, particularly to demonstrate the capabilities of the new statistical methods. In this investigation, our objective was to prevent unnecessary false positive results, hence a more stringent significance threshold was instituted. The significance level (P Value) for each individual hypothesis should, therefore, be 0.016 or less. Assuming that the data collected by El-Khier are highly precise and closely approximate reality, we are warranted in positing that a Parvovirus B19 infection is a necessary condition for acute myeloid leukaemia (Table 35). In other words, **without** Parvovirus B19 infection, **no** acute myeloid leukaemia (P Value < 0.016). Furthermore, the data collected by El-Khier provide grounds to infer that a Parvovirus B19 infection is also a sufficient condition for acute myeloid leukaemia (Table 36). Put colloquially, **if** Parvovirus B19 infection, **then** acute myeloid leukaemia (P Value < 0.016).

To decisively ascertain the question of causality between two events, it is highly advantageous if studies have been able to demonstrate a significant necessary condition between the two examined events. In this regard, the proof of a significant sufficient condition between two examined events should also be attainable. Under these conditions, two essential prerequisites would be met to contemplate the possibility of a causal relationship between the two examined events. Due to study designs and other factors, a singular study is unlikely to provide both proofs in rare instances. Additionally, it is highly appropriate to present direct evidence, for instance, in the form of a significant necessary and sufficient condition (Table 37), to assess the question of causality with great confidence and potentially conclusively.

The data from El-Khier et al. substantiate the hypothesis that a Parvovirus B19 infection is simultaneously a necessary and sufficient condition for acute myeloid leukaemia. In the comprehensive review of El-Khier et al.'s data, we have grounds to infer that a Parvovirus B19 infection is the cause of acute myeloid leukaemia ($k = +0,92890808$; P Value = 0). A pilot study with a small sample size may encounter challenges such as limited generalizability, reduced statistical power, and potential difficulty in detecting significant effects. These limitations can impede the external validity of the findings and compromise the ability to draw robust conclusions about the broader population. Consequently, caution must be exercised when extrapolating the outcomes of such studies to larger contexts, and results should be interpreted with awareness of the inherent limitations associated with the constrained sample size. However, despite all potential constraints, the question arises as to how El-Khier et al. could have gathered the published data. The probability that these data arose purely by chance is not zero, but is also not significantly distant from zero.

5. Conclusion

Certainly, further and more meticulous investigations in this realm are imperative and urgently warranted to unravel the intricacies of the underlying mechanisms and to delve into potential therapeutic interventions. Clarifying the causal relationship between Parvovirus B19 and AML holds significant promise for shaping effective prevention and treatment strategies. Nevertheless, we anticipate, with a high degree of confidence, that the outcome will remain substantially unaltered: Parvovirus B19 is the cause of acute myeloid leukaemia.

Acknowledgments

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

Private note

The definition section of a paper need not and does not necessarily contain new scientific aspects. Above all, it also serves to better understand a scientific publication, to follow every step of the arguments of an author and to explain in greater details the fundamentals on which a publication is based. Therefore, there is no objective need to force authors to reinvent a scientific wheel once and again unless such a need appears obviously factually necessary. The effort to write about a certain subject in an original way in multiple publications does not exclude the necessity simply to cut and paste from an earlier work, and has nothing to do with self-plagiarism. However, such an attitude cannot simply be transferred to the sections' introduction, results, discussion and conclusions et cetera.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are frequently used:

CMV	Cytomegalovirus
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBV	Epstein-Bar virus
IHC	Immunohistochemistry
ISH	In situ hybridization
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
BMI	body mass index
ESRD	end-stage renal disease
HD	hemodialysis
CABG	coronary artery bypass graft
CCI	Charlson comorbidity index
AMI	acute myocardial infarction
MACE	major adverse cardiovascular events
LDL-C	low-density lipoprotein cholesterol
GFR	glomerular filtration rate
STEMI	ST elevation myocardial infarction
NSTEMI	non-ST elevation myocardial infarction
MI	myocardial infarction
ARB	angiotensin receptor blocker
ACEI	angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors
CCBs	calcium channel blockers
IOR	index of relationship
p(IOU)	index of unfairness
p(IOI)	index of independence
k	Causal relationship
SINE	Necessary condition relationship
IMP	Sufficient condition relationship
EXCL	exclusion relationship
RR	Relative risk
RR (nc)	relative risk (necessary condition)
RR (sc)	relative risk (sufficient condition)
OR	Odds ratio
P Value	Probability of significance

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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